

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN

Master Thesis

**Anomaly Detection in Traffic Applications:
A Probabilistic Forecasting Approach Based on
Object Tracking**

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Tools used: *OpenAI ChatGPT* (models: *o4-mini* and *GPT-5*; accessed in 2025)

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Abstract

Traffic anomaly detection is a critical challenge at the intersection of computer vision, machine learning, and intelligent transportation systems. This thesis addresses anomaly detection in static overhead traffic scenes, such as intersections and roundabouts, where anomalies appear often subtle at the pixel level due to high camera placement and dense traffic, and are often context-dependent and interaction-based. Unlike prior approaches based on video reconstruction or future-frame prediction, this thesis proposes a *Probabilistic Movement Forecaster* (PMF) that conditions on current detections and surrounding traffic agents to estimate the plausibility of near-future motion.

The PMF outputs probabilistic forecasts of vehicle positions and derives anomaly scores from predicted and observed outcomes. Three innovations are introduced: (i) explicit context integration of neighboring agents, (ii) distance-aware regularization of covariance estimates, and (iii) asymmetric scoring to improve sensitivity to direction-specific uncertainties. These scores are aggregated into trajectory-level measures using ranking-based functions, with exponentially weighted averaging proving robust and effective across diverse scenes.

To evaluate the approach, a dataset is created comprising three urban camera locations with over 1,000 annotated anomalies across 32 fine-grained categories and graded relevance levels. Evaluation with normalized discounted cumulative gain (NDCG) and area under the precision–recall curve (AU-PR) demonstrates that the PMF consistently detects and prioritizes critical anomalies, while remaining resilient to detection and tracking noise. The dataset, including complete background traffic, establishes a benchmark for future work that can be easily extended.

This thesis shows that probabilistic motion forecasting, combined with severity-aware ranking metrics, provides a principled and practical basis for anomaly detection in complex traffic environments.

Kurzfassung

Die Detektion von Anomalien im Straßenverkehr stellt eine zentrale Herausforderung an der Schnittstelle von Computer Vision, Maschinellem Lernen und Intelligenten Transportsystemen dar. Diese Arbeit behandelt das Problem in statischen Überwachungsszenen aus der Vogelperspektive, etwa an Kreuzungen und Kreisverkehren, wo Anomalien aufgrund der Vielzahl gleichzeitig sichtbarer Bewegungen auf Pixelebene oft nur subtil erkennbar sind und zudem stark kontext- und interaktionsabhängig auftreten. Anders als existierende Ansätze, die auf Videorekonstruktion oder Zukunfts-Frame-Vorhersagen beruhen, wird in dieser Arbeit ein *Probabilistic Movement Forecaster* (PMF) vorgestellt, der aktuelle Detektionen und umliegende Verkehrsteilnehmer berücksichtigt, um die Plausibilität zukünftiger Bewegungen zu bewerten.

Der PMF erzeugt probabilistische Vorhersagen zukünftiger Fahrzeugpositionen und leitet Anomaliescores aus der Abweichung zwischen vorhergesagten und beobachteten Positionen ab. Dabei werden drei wesentliche Neuerungen eingeführt: (i) die explizite Integration benachbarter Verkehrsteilnehmer, (ii) eine distanzabhängige Regularisierung der Kovarianzschätzung und (iii) ein asymmetrisches Scoring zur verbesserten Sensitivität gegenüber richtungsspezifischen Unsicherheiten. Die resultierenden Werte werden mithilfe rangbasierter Funktionen zu Trajektorien-Scores aggregiert, wobei sich exponentiell gewichtete Mittelwerte als besonders robust und effektiv erwiesen haben.

Für die Evaluation wurde ein Datensatz mit Szenen aus drei urbanen Kameras erstellt, der über 1.000 annotierte Anomalien in 32 fein abgestuften Kategorien und Relevanzgraden umfasst. Die Bewertung mit den Metriken Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (NDCG) und der Fläche unter der Precision-Recall-Kurve (AU-PR) zeigt, dass der PMF sicherheitskritische Anomalien zuverlässig erkennt, priorisiert und zugleich robust gegenüber Detektions- und Tracking-Fehlern bleibt. Der Datensatz, der den vollständigen Verkehrsfluss einschließt, stellt eine belastbare Grundlage für zukünftige Arbeiten dar und kann problemlos erweitert werden.

Diese Arbeit zeigt, dass probabilistische Bewegungsprognosen in Kombination mit Relevanz-bewussten Rangmetriken eine fundierte und praxisnahe Basis für die Anomalieerkennung in komplexen Verkehrsszenen bilden.

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List of Acronyms

AE	autoencoder
AnDe	anomaly detection
ASYM δ	PMF model with asymmetrical output distribution and prediction horizon δ
AU-PR	area under the precision–recall curve
AU-ROC	area under the receiver operating characteristic curve
bbox	bounding box
CNN	convolutional neural network
DCG	discounted cumulative gain
DBSCAN	density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise
DoTA	detection of traffic anomaly
ELBO	evidence lower bound
FLOPs	floating-point operations (computational complexity)
FP	false positive
FPR	false positive rate
FPS	frames per second
FN	false negative
GMM	Gaussian mixture model
IDCG	ideal discounted cumulative gain
i.i.d.	independent and identically distributed
KDE	kernel density estimation
kNN	k -nearest neighbors
lin	linearly
LSTM	long short-term memory network
MOT	multi-object tracking
MSE	mean squared error
NDCG	normalized discounted cumulative gain
NLL	negative log-likelihood
NN	nearest neighbor
NNC	nearest neighbor-based clustering
PMF	probabilistic movement forecaster
SAE	Starwit Awareness Engine
SOTA	state-of-the-art
SYM δ	PMF model with symmetrical output distribution and prediction horizon δ
TN	true negative
TP	true positive
VAE	variational autoencoder
YOLO	You Only Look Once (object detector)

List of Symbols

General symbols

\mathcal{D}	dataset
$ \mathcal{D} , N$	number of samples in the dataset
x_i	i -th sample in the dataset (vector)
d	dimensionality of samples ($d \in \mathbb{N}$)
x_t	sample at time step t
$x_{t_1:t_2}$	sequence of samples x_{t_1}, \dots, x_{t_2}
$x^{(k)}$	k -th sample in a sorted list
x^*	sample at inference time
\hat{x}	model prediction for x
x^\top	transpose of vector x
$\ x\ $	norm of x
$\lfloor k \rfloor$	floor function (rounding down)
\forall	universal quantifier
\mathcal{N}	Gaussian distribution
μ	mean of a Gaussian distribution
σ	standard deviation of a univariate Gaussian
Σ	covariance matrix of a multivariate Gaussian
$x \sim p$	random variable x distributed as p
$p(x)$	probability distribution over x
$p(x y)$	conditional probability of x given y
$\mathbb{E}_{p(x y)}[t(x)]$	expectation of $t(x)$ under $p(x y)$
I	identity matrix
A^{-1}	inverse of matrix A
$ A $	determinant of matrix A
v	eigenvector
λ	eigenvalue
h	smoothing bandwidth in kernel density estimation
\mathcal{O}	computational complexity

Functions and Operators

$f(x)$	probability density function
$\exp(x)$	exponential function e^x
$\text{sgn}(x)$	sign function: -1 if $x < 0$, 1 if $x \geq 0$
$\max_x f(x)$	maximum of f with respect to x
$\text{dist}(x_i, x_j)$	distance between x_i and x_j
$D_M(x; \mu, \Sigma)$	Mahalanobis distance of x to μ , scaled by Σ (also notated as $D_{M,\text{sym}}$)
$K(x)$	kernel function
$D_{\text{KL}}(q p)$	Kullback–Leibler (KL) divergence of q and p
$f_\theta(x)$	model with parameters θ
$f_\phi(x)$	encoder function with parameters ϕ
$g_\theta(x)$	decoder function with parameters θ
$q_\phi(z x)$	probabilistic encoder distribution
$p_\theta(x z)$	probabilistic decoder distribution
\mathcal{L}	loss function
$\int_0^1 f(\vartheta) d\vartheta$	integral over $[0, 1]$
$\frac{d}{d\vartheta} f(\vartheta)$	derivative of $f(\vartheta)$ with respect to ϑ

Anomaly Detection

γ	upper cutoff threshold on probability density (flag anomalies below γ)
τ	lower cutoff threshold on anomaly scores (flag anomalies above τ)
$s(x)$	anomaly score of sample x (higher means more anomalous)
$\Phi(f)$	monotonically decreasing function on density f used to define s
$s_{t,j}$	anomaly score of agent j at time step t
$s_{(k),j}$	k -th largest anomaly score among all s of trajectory T_j
score_j	trajectory-level anomaly score for T_j
$\text{score}^{(k)}(j)$	trajectory score based on the k -th ranked score $s_{(k),j}$
$\text{score}_{\text{aggr}}^{(k)}(j)$	trajectory score aggregating the top- k scores of T_j based on <i>aggr</i>
$\text{score}_{\text{aggr}}^{(p)}(j)$	trajectory score aggregating scores above percentile p of T_j based on <i>aggr</i>
a	exponential weighting parameter
$\text{score}_{\text{exp}}^{(a)}(j)$	trajectory score using exponentially weighted average of all s in T_j

Neighbor-based Clustering (NNC)

ϵ	neighborhood radius around a sample
MinPts	minimum number of points within a neighborhood to be considered dense
\mathcal{N}_{ij}	set of all points within radius ϵ of a sample
\mathcal{C}_{ij}	number of clusters in neighborhood \mathcal{N}_{ij}
ϵ_θ	angular neighborhood radius used in DBSCAN clustering
z	z -score (standardized value)

Probabilistic Motion Forecaster (PMF)

δ	prediction horizon (time in seconds)
$C_{t+\delta,j}$	ground-truth position (bbox center) of agent j at time $t + \delta$
$\hat{C}_{t+\delta,j}$	predicted expected position of agent j at time $t + \delta$
$\Sigma_{t+\delta,j}$	predicted covariance matrix (uncertainty) for $\hat{C}_{t+\delta,j}$
λ	skew parameters for rescaling the output distribution
ϵ	error vector (distance between C and \hat{C})
$\epsilon^{(\text{skewed})}$	skewed error vector used in asymmetrical Mahalanobis distance
$D_{\text{M,sym}}(C; \hat{C}, \Sigma)$	Mahalanobis distance variant with symmetric covariance matrix
$D_{\text{M,asym}}(C; \hat{C}, \Sigma, \lambda)$	asymmetrical Mahalanobis distance with skew parameters
$\mathcal{L}_{\text{sym}}(C; \hat{C}, \Sigma)$	loss function for symmetric model
$\mathcal{L}_{\text{asym}}(C; \hat{C}, \Sigma, \lambda)$	loss function for asymmetrical model
\mathcal{R}	regularization term in loss \mathcal{L}
α	covariance regularization parameter (based on bounding-box size)
$\tilde{\alpha}$	penalty factor in covariance regularization
β	penalty factor in L2 regularization of skew parameters λ

Object Detection and Tracking

t	time step (scene or frame at time t)
det	object detection (bounding box b + class label cl)
D_t	set of all detections at time step t
det $_{t,i}$	i -th detection at time step t
$b_{t,i}$	bounding box of the i -th detection at t , coordinates $(x_{\min}, y_{\min}, x_{\max}, y_{\max})$
cl $_{t,i}$	class label of the i -th detection at time step t
j	unique agent ID (traffic participant)
tr $_{t,i}$	track: i -th detection at time step t with its associated agent ID j
\mathcal{T}_t	set of all tracks at time step t
T_j	trajectory of agent j (all tracks with ID j)
T_j^t	partial trajectory of agent j , including tracks tr $_{1,j}, \dots, \text{tr}_{t,j}$
N_j	number of tracks in trajectory T_j
C	center point of bounding box b
b_{smooth}	smoothed bounding box (after trajectory smoothing)
C_{smooth}	center point of the smoothed bounding box b_{smooth}
θ	motion angle (direction of movement)
$\bar{\theta}$	mean motion angle (average direction of movement)
tr'	smoothed track with motion angle: det (with b_{smooth}), agent ID j , and θ
T'_j	preprocessed trajectory: set of all tr' for agent j

1 Introduction

Traffic anomaly detection is an important problem at the intersection of computer vision, machine learning, and intelligent transportation systems. This thesis addresses the challenge in the specific context of *static overhead cameras*, which monitor complex intersections and roundabouts.

This introductory chapter first motivates the problem and its industrial relevance, then defines the objectives of this thesis, and finally outlines the structure of the document.

1.1 Motivation and Background

Ensuring road safety is a central challenge in modern urban environments. Many risky situations in traffic arise from *unusual driving behavior* such as wrong-way driving, excessive speeding, abrupt cutoffs, or crashes. Detecting such anomalous behavior is of high practical importance. It allows early warnings of dangerous incidents, supports automated notification of police or traffic authorities, and enables systematic collection of statistics on how traffic risks differ across urban locations. Figure 1.1 illustrates typical anomalies of interest: wrong-way drivers, collisions and drivers leaving road or failing to yield.

From a methodological perspective, detecting unusual traffic behavior is best approached as an *anomaly detection* problem: most vehicle movements follow predictable, lawful patterns, while only a small fraction deviate in ways that may signal risk. Supervised classification would in principle allow distinguishing between normal and anomalous cases, but in practice it requires extensive annotation of every relevant anomaly type, which is both costly and unrealistic given their rarity and diversity. For this reason, unsupervised and self-supervised methods are far better suited. They learn directly from long-term video of regular traffic and flag deviations without the need for explicit labels, making them particularly effective in real-world traffic scenes. [CBK09, YWX⁺23a]

Beyond safety, anomaly detection also serves broader goals in traffic management and urban planning. Statistical analysis of unusual behavior across intersections or roundabouts can reveal which locations are most prone to risky events and why. For example, one scene may be dominated by near-collisions due to high traffic density, while another may frequently show vehicles cutting corners due to ambiguous road markings. Insights of this kind are valuable for infrastructure design, enforcement strategies, and prioritizing safety investments.

A further driver of this research is its industrial relevance. This Master's thesis is conducted in cooperation with *Starwit Technologies GmbH*, a startup specializing in intelligent traffic monitoring and Smart City solutions. Starwit currently operates detection and

Figure 1.1: Representative traffic anomalies in overhead surveillance (examples from our cameras at Starwit): wrong-way driving, leaving the road, failing to yield, and collisions.

tracking modules for traffic agents, like vehicles, bicycles and pedestrians. However, Starwit lacks dedicated systems for identifying unusual or risky behavior. Developing anomaly detection for static overhead cameras at busy intersections and roundabouts thus represents both a new research challenge and a practical application.

Unlike much of the existing work, which focuses on dashcam or frontal-view perspectives [LLLG18, YWX⁺23b], static overhead views provide a stable perspective with minimal egomotion but introduce their own challenges: anomalies are often subtle and context-dependent, such as a wrong-way driver appearing as a straight trajectory or a failure to yield that is only visible when comparing multiple vehicles' motions. Yet, large-scale datasets for this setting are scarce. Existing benchmarks such as DoTA [YWX⁺23a], UMAD [BOJ⁺24], or Street Scene [RJ19] target either dashcam or general surveillance footage and do not capture dense, multi-lane intersection views like roundabouts. This gap underscores the need for specialized methods and datasets tailored to static overhead scenes.

At an abstract level, anomaly detection distinguishes between data consistent with "normal" behavior and data that deviates. This task is particularly challenging because the boundary between normal and anomalous behavior is often imprecise, especially in traffic scenarios where certain actions represent borderline violations rather than clear outliers. Moreover, anomalies are inherently rare and highly diverse, ranging from subtle hesitation to catastrophic crashes. Labeling such events is costly and subjective, as some cases may fit multiple categories or fall ambiguously between them. Finally, traffic patterns evolve over time, requiring models that can adapt to changing conditions. These challenges have led to domain-specific formulations, with trajectory-based anomaly detection in surveillance video becoming a central approach. [CBK09, SDR20]

1.2 Objectives

The main objective of this thesis is to develop an *unsupervised, probabilistic* framework, the probabilistic movement forecaster (PMF), for anomaly detection in static overhead traffic scenes. Without relying on large-scale manual annotation, the method should learn motion plausibility directly from regular traffic video.

The traffic anomaly system is expected to:

- estimate the plausibility of individual vehicle motions by conditioning on surrounding traffic context,
- detect anomalies at the level of individual agent detections and whole trajectories, while remaining robust to detection and tracking errors, and
- rank anomalies by severity, enabling prioritization of the most safety-critical cases.

Beyond the system itself, the thesis also aims to:

- provide a benchmark dataset of urban traffic scenes with fine-grained anomaly labels and graded relevance levels, establishing a basis for systematic evaluation, and
- compare the PMF against a common machine-learning baseline, motion clustering, to highlight the benefits of probabilistic forecasting over traditional unsupervised approaches.

By addressing these objectives, the thesis advances both the methodological foundations of probabilistic traffic anomaly detection and its practical deployment in real-world monitoring systems, through its integration into Smart City projects in cooperation with Starwit Technologies GmbH.

This thesis assumes that the reader is familiar with fundamental machine learning concepts, including basic probability and statistics, neural networks, and standard evaluation metrics. The exposition therefore focuses on the proposed methods and empirical analysis rather than introductory material.

1.3 Outline

The structure of this thesis is organized as follows:

This chapter, **Chapter 1**, introduces the problem of traffic anomaly detection, outlines the motivation and objectives of this work, and presents the industrial context in cooperation with Starwit Technologies GmbH.

Chapter 2 provides the theoretical and methodological foundations. It begins with a formal definition of anomaly detection and classical statistical methods, then reviews modern deep-learning approaches. The chapter further discusses evaluation metrics for anomaly detection and the role of agent detection and tracking as essential preprocessing steps. Finally, it surveys state-of-the-art methods for traffic anomaly detection, with emphasis on the unique challenges of static overhead views.

2 Foundations and Related Work

This chapter introduces the theoretical and methodological foundations of anomaly detection with emphasis on traffic surveillance. We begin with general principles of anomaly detection, covering definitions, classical methods, deep learning, and evaluation metrics in Section 2.1. Section 2.2 covers detection and tracking as essential preprocessing steps, before highlighting recent advances in traffic-specific anomaly detection in Section 2.3.

2.1 Fundamentals of Anomaly Detection

Anomaly detection aims to identify data patterns that deviate from expected or normal behavior. We outline a formal definition, key challenges such as label scarcity and diverse anomaly types, and review approaches from statistical baselines to deep learning. We conclude with an overview of common evaluation metrics.

2.1.1 Definition Anomaly Detection

Anomalies are patterns in data that do not fit a well-defined notion of normal behavior. There are various reasons for anomalies appearing in data, such as, malicious activity, credit card fraud, or a break-down of a system. Anomalies have one common characteristic, that they are interesting to the analyst. Anomaly Detection is the process of identifying such points or patterns that deviate from normal behavior. [CBK09]

Formally, let $\mathcal{D} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\}$ be a set of random observations with each $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ [Che17]. We assume these observations can be characterized by an underlying probability density function, which we denote as $f_{\text{normal}}(x)$. This density function is typically learned or estimated by a model. A point $x_i \in \mathcal{D}$ is declared an anomaly if its likelihood under this density falls below a certain threshold γ :

$$x_i \text{ is an anomaly if } f_{\text{normal}}(x_i) < \gamma. \quad (2.1)$$

Equivalently, Anomaly Detection Methods often define an outlier score

$$s(x) = \Phi(f_{\text{normal}}(x)) \quad (2.2)$$

where Φ is a monotonically decreasing function, so that a higher score corresponds to a lower likelihood under $f_{\text{normal}}(x)$, leading to the following decision boundary with lower cutoff-threshold τ :

$$x_i \text{ is an anomaly if } s(x_i) > \tau. \quad (2.3)$$

Figure 2.1: Example of anomalies in a two-dimensional dataset (Source: [CBK09]).

In short, an anomaly is any $x_i \in \mathcal{D}$ whose generation probability or density under the learned model of normal data is significantly lower than that of the other data points [Agg16].

Figure 2.1 illustrates anomalies in a two-dimensional setting. Here the data \mathcal{D} has two normal regions, N_1 and N_2 containing most of the observations. Points that are sufficiently far away from these regions, for example, points o_1 and o_2 , and points in region O_3 , are anomalies. It is important to mention the distinction between noise and real anomalies. Noise comes from random errors during measurement or irregular data acquisition while anomalies represent systematic outliers that are the result of hidden events or frauds. The practical significance or real-life relevance of anomalies is a key feature of anomaly detection [CBK09].

Depending on the context, anomalies can be divided into three main types: point anomalies, contextual anomalies, and collective anomalies [CBK09]. Point anomalies are single data points that appear unusual when observed individually. Contextual anomalies are points whose deviation from the usual is only unusual in a specific context, such as context in time and space. An example is a temperature of 20 degrees in German winter. The third category, collective anomalies, consists of groups of data points that are not suspicious when observed individually but appear unusual together, such as a short-term pattern in sequence data.

The motivation for anomaly detection spans many application domains, such as IT security in terms of detecting network intrusions, industrial settings where the early identification of machine failures is important, fraud detection in finance and video analysis [Agg16, CBK09]. This master thesis captures an application of video analysis which is identifying unusual traffic movements. In particular, within traffic surveillance, the detection of unusual vehicle behavior is crucial for the early recognition of accidents or traffic jams.

A huge challenge in anomaly detection are data labels. Typically, getting a labeled set of anomalous data samples that covers all possible types of anomalous behavior is far more difficult than getting labels for normal behavior because these events are rare and

often unexpected. Additionally, the anomalous behavior may be dynamic in nature, meaning new types of anomalies might arise, for which there is no labeled training data. Based on the extent to which the labels are available, anomaly detection techniques can operate in one of the following three modes: Supervised, semi-supervised or unsupervised. Techniques trained in supervised mode assume the availability of a training data set that has labeled instances for both, normal and anomaly classes. In the semi-supervised mode, we assume that the training data has labeled instances only for the normal class and in the unsupervised mode we do not require any labels. In the unsupervised case, self-supervised learning strategies are very powerful. Here the model generates its own training labels from the structure of the input data. [CBK09]

Anomaly detection methods can be divided into two categories: classical approaches and deep-learning techniques. Classical methods include parametric models, such as assuming a Gaussian distribution for the data, as well as non-parametric density estimators like kernel density estimation. Nearest neighbor-based and clustering-based techniques also fall under this category. Deep learning methods, on the other hand, can be split into reconstruction-based approaches like autoencoders, as well as sequence and prediction-based methods [CBK09]. Below, Section 2.1.2 will cover the statistical techniques while section 2.1.3 will then detail deep learning approaches, giving special attention to foundations that are important for advanced traffic anomaly detection.

In our traffic video scenes, no labels are available, so we rely on unsupervised and self-supervised techniques rather than fully supervised classifiers. Moreover, a label-free workflow allows us to train the same model on raw video data in new scenes without any human annotation effort. Thus, the following sections will focus on unsupervised approaches.

2.1.2 Statistical and Classical Machine Learning Methods

Following the formal definition in section 2.1.1, we now describe some common classical anomaly detection techniques. These methods are typically easy to implement and require relatively little data to achieve meaningful results. Moreover, their interpretability makes them well-suited for applications where transparency and explainability are essential. However, most of these methods rely on the assumption that data points are independently and identically distributed (i.i.d.), which limits their effectiveness in capturing dependencies in sequential or structured data. As a result, they are often insufficient for high-dimensional, sequential, or visual data, but provide the foundation for some of the advanced deep learning approaches and will later provide a comparison baseline for our proposed method.

Parametric Models: Gaussian Distribution and Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM)

Parametric models assume that the normal data is drawn from a certain kind of distribution. The goal is to only fit the distribution parameters. A Gaussian model assumes the normal data distribution is a multivariate Gaussian. There is no need in fitting a whole

Figure 2.2: Illustration of two anomaly detection methods in a two-dimensional space. (a) The Mahalanobis distance defines an elliptical boundary based on the covariance matrix Σ ; eigenvectors v_i determine the ellipse axes, and eigenvalues λ_i their lengths. (b) KDE combines individual Gaussian kernels (gray circles) to form a smooth estimate of the data distribution.

unknown distribution but only the parameters $\mu \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $\Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$: $\mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i$, $\Sigma = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)(x_i - \mu)^\top$ [Pri12]. The density is

$$f_{\text{Gaussian}}(x) = \mathcal{N}(x; \mu, \Sigma) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{d/2} |\Sigma|^{1/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} (x - \mu)^\top \Sigma^{-1} (x - \mu)\right). \quad (2.4)$$

A point x_j is declared an anomaly if $f_{\text{Gaussian}}(x_j) < \gamma$ or equivalently by using the squared Mahalanobis distance as an outlier scoring:

$$D_M^2(x_j; \mu, \Sigma) = (x_j - \mu)^\top \Sigma^{-1} (x_j - \mu) > \tau, \quad (2.5)$$

The Mahalanobis distance measures the distance of a point x_j to the mean μ , scaled by the data covariance Σ . Different from the simple Euclidean distance, the Mahalanobis distance accounts for feature variances and their correlations [Gho19]. Figure 2.2a shows a Mahalanobis-distance contour, blue ellipse, which defines the decision threshold $D_M^2(x; \mu, \Sigma) = \tau$. The dots inside the ellipse are typical inliers generated from the assumed bivariate Gaussian, while the single red point outside represents an outlier since its Mahalanobis distance exceeds the boundary.

This parametric Gaussian approach has significant limitations because it requires the normal data to be approximately Gaussian. Although the parameters can be estimated simply via maximum likelihood, a single Gaussian often fails on multimodal data.

However, this baseline approach can generalize to a Gaussian mixture model (GMM) to handle multiple modes, making it more adaptable to diverse distributions [Rey09]. These models assume that the normal data are generated from a mixture of K multivariate Gaussian components rather than a single Gaussian. Formally, the density is written as

$$f_{\text{GMM}}(x) = \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \mathcal{N}(x; \mu_k, \Sigma_k), \quad \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k = 1, \quad \pi_k \geq 0. \quad (2.6)$$

Each individual component density is weighted by a factor π_k . This allows for a more flexible decision boundary that is a union of several Mahalanobis ellipsoids, allowing complex normal regions. However, GMMs often require careful selection of the number of components K , leading to overfitting or poor convergence on high-dimensional or limited data. Another disadvantage is that during fitting, the components can suffer from mode collapse, meaning they are assigned near zero weight or several components converge to the same mode. [Rey09]

Non-parametric Density Estimation: Kernel Density Estimation (KDE)

In the non-parametric case there is no restriction of assuming a fixed distribution family for the underlying probability density function of a dataset. A well-known non-parametric density estimator is kernel density estimation (KDE), also known as the Parzen's window [Par62], that automatically learns the shape of the density from the data. Formally, given the training data set $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^N$ where each x_i is i.i.d., we can calculate:

$$f_{\text{KDE}}(x) = \frac{1}{Nh^d} \sum_{i=1}^N K\left(\frac{x - x_i}{h}\right), \quad (2.7)$$

where $K : \mathbb{R}^d \mapsto \mathbb{R}^+$ is the kernel function and $h > 0$ is the smoothing bandwidth that controls the amount of smoothing. The bandwidth is often a matrix H in practice which allows a different amount of smoothing in every direction [Che17]. A common example of $K(x)$ is the Gaussian kernel:

$$K(x) = (2\pi)^{-d/2} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\|u\|^2\right). \quad (2.8)$$

KDE has the effect of smoothing out each data point of the training set into a smooth bump whose shape is determined by the kernel function $K(x)$. Then, KDE sums over all these bumps to obtain a density estimator. [Che17]

Figure 2.2b shows an example for two-dimensional data. At regions with many observations, KDE will yield a large value. However, for regions with only a few observations, the density value from summing over the bumps is low. Instances in these regions are labeled anomalies: x_j is anomalous if $f_{\text{KDE}}(x_j) < \gamma$.

While KDE is purely data-driven, it has notable drawbacks. The computational complexity is $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ and it demands careful selection of the bandwidth h . Moreover, KDE suffers from the curse of dimensionality. As the feature-space dimension d increases, data become sparse, causing the density estimates to become unreliable and flatten out. Lastly, KDE requires storing all training samples in memory.

Nearest Neighbor-Based Techniques

There are several anomaly detection techniques based on the concept of nearest neighbor (NN) analysis. Such techniques are based on the common key assumption: normal data instances occur in dense neighborhoods, while anomalies occur far from their closest neighbors. Nearest neighbor-based anomaly detection techniques require a distance or similarity measure defined between two data instances. [CBK09]

One practice (kNN) is to score each sample $x_j \in \mathcal{D}$ based on the distance to its k -th nearest neighbor ($x_{(k)}$): $s_{kNN}(x_j) = \text{dist}(x_j, x_{(k)})$. If x_j lies far from its neighbors, it is likely an outlier. In this method a small k is sensitive to local noise and, on the other hand, a large k is more robust but may miss some small isolated anomalies. Some other approaches instead fix a radius r and only count the neighbors that are not more than r distance apart from the given data instance, resulting in a scoring function based on the number of near samples. [CBK09]

While these approaches are also purely data driven and do not make any assumptions regarding the data distribution, there are some disadvantages. The computational complexity of the basic technique is again $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ and it suffers from the curse of dimensionality. Here, as the feature-space dimension d increases, the pairwise distances of the samples tend to concentrate, making it hard to distinguish anomalies from normal points. Also, all training samples need to be stored in memory.

Clustering-Based Technique: Density-Based Spatial Clustering (DBSCAN)

Clustering is used to group similar data instances together. It is primarily an unsupervised method that can be used in different ways for anomaly detection. Here, we shortly present the density-based spatial Clustering (DBSCAN) [EK SX96] technique.

DBSCAN groups points into dense regions and labels any point that does not belong to a dense cluster as an outlier, a potential anomaly. It requires two parameters: a radius ϵ for defining the neighborhood, called the Eps-neighborhood, and a minimum number of points MinPts within the neighborhood to consider that region dense. To find a cluster, DBSCAN starts with an arbitrary point and retrieves all points density-reachable from it based on the parameters ϵ and MinPts. A point x is then considered a core point if $|\{y \in \mathcal{D} | \text{dist}(x, y) \leq \epsilon\}| \geq \text{MinPts}$. Further, a border point is a point that is not a core point but lies within ϵ of some core point. An anomaly, a noise point, is neither a core nor a border point. New clusters are formed by starting from unvisited points. If it is a core point, all points density-reachable via neighboring core points are gathered. Points never assigned to any cluster remain labeled as noise points. [EK SX96]

DBSCAN can discover arbitrarily shaped clusters and is robust to outliers, making it suitable for anomaly detection. It also does not require specifying the number of clusters in advance, but it can be highly sensitive to its hyperparameters ϵ and MinPts, and may struggle to detect anomalies correctly in datasets with widely varying density.

2.1.3 Deep Learning Methods for Anomaly Detection

Deep learning methods have become powerful tools for modeling complex data distributions and uncovering high-dimensional structures. In the context of anomaly detection, deep neural networks are typically applied in a self-supervised or unsupervised fashion, which is very important for our use case. This section presents state-of-the-art (SOTA) concepts and methods, which form the theoretical basis for our proposed model.

Reconstruction-Based Models

Reconstruction-based approaches aim to learn a latent representation of the input such that the model can reconstruct the original input from that representation with minimal error. The assumption is that a model trained only on normal data will fail to accurately reconstruct anomalous inputs. A widely used model architecture for the reconstruction task is the autoencoder (AE).

Formally, a classical AE model consists of an encoder function $f_\phi(x)$ that maps an input $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ into a lower-dimensional latent space z , and a decoder $g_\theta(z)$ that reconstructs the original input [NT24]. Both the encoder and decoder functions are typically implemented as deep neural networks with parameters ϕ and θ . The reconstruction loss is usually defined as the mean squared error (MSE) between the input and its reconstruction:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}}(x) = \|x - g_\theta(f_\phi(x))\|^2. \quad (2.9)$$

A well-trained AE is expected to achieve low reconstruction error on normal, usual samples it has seen during training or on inputs that are similar to them. A high reconstruction error, on the other hand, indicates that the input deviates from the training distribution and is thus likely to be anomalous. In this context, the reconstruction loss can be used directly as an outlier score $s_{\text{AE}}(x) = \mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}}(x)$. The approach can be used in semi-supervised or unsupervised mode. In the semi-supervised case, only the normal data is used for training, leading to a higher anomaly detection accuracy. However, this method does not explicitly model uncertainty and probability distributions [AC15].

To enable probabilistic reasoning, the Variational Autoencoder (VAE) was introduced by Kingma and Welling [KW14]. It models the encoder as a distribution $q_\phi(z|x)$, typically Gaussian, and defines the decoder probabilistically via $p_\theta(x|z)$. In this framework, the latent variable $z \sim p(z) = \mathcal{N}(0, I)$ captures hidden structure.

The model is trained by maximizing the evidence lower bound (ELBO), defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{VAE}}(x) = \mathbb{E}_{q_\phi(z|x)}[\log p_\theta(x|z)] - D_{\text{KL}}(q_\phi(z|x) \| p(z)), \quad (2.10)$$

where $\mathbb{E}_{q_\phi(z|x)}[t(z)]$ denotes the expectation of $t(z)$ under the distribution $q_\phi(z|x)$, i.e. with $z \sim q_\phi(z|x)$. D_{KL} is the KL-divergence between the distributions q_θ and p .

This leads to a probabilistic reconstruction error and supports sampling-based anomaly scoring. During inference, multiple samples are drawn from the encoder distribution and passed through the decoder to reconstruct the input. The anomaly score is then computed as the negative log-likelihood of the input under the model’s reconstruction distribution. An and Cho [AC15] refer to this scoring method as the reconstruction probability.

In general, reconstruction-based methods are well suited for data types that have strong spatial or structural regularities. This includes image data, video frames, or graph-structured data. Anomalies in such domains typically appear as localized deviations from the normal structure and therefore lead to a higher reconstruction error. For this reason, autoencoders and variational autoencoders are widely used in areas such as industrial inspection, medical image analysis, or molecule structure modeling.

From Reconstruction to Sequence Models: LSTM and Transformer Autoencoders

To better capture the sequential nature of time-series or trajectory data, autoencoders can be extended with recurrent layers. In a sequence-to-sequence Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) autoencoder [MRA⁺16], both the encoder and decoder are implemented using LSTM networks that process input windows of temporal data. The model learns to reconstruct the sequence, and anomalies are again detected based on reconstruction error over time.

Recently, Transformer models have become a powerful alternative to recurrent models for sequence modeling. Transformer architectures, originally developed for natural language processing by Vaswani et al. [VSP⁺17], leverage self-attention mechanisms to capture global dependencies across input sequences or spatial patches. In the time-series domain, each timestep or feature vector can be treated as a token in a sequence, similar to words in a sentence. [LWLQ21]

The encoder of a Transformer autoencoder maps the entire sequence into a set of latent representations using multi-head self-attention, allowing the model to learn relationships across distant timesteps without recurrence. The decoder then reconstructs the sequence from this latent representation, either autoregressively or in parallel. Compared to LSTM-based models, Transformer autoencoders offer higher parallelization, better handling of long-range dependencies, and increased flexibility in modeling complex patterns in spatiotemporal data. [LWLQ21]

However, LSTM and Transformer autoencoders do not predict future values and simply reconstructing the input is often not enough to detect temporal irregularities or context-dependent deviations. Nevertheless, when combined with attention mechanisms and probabilistic modeling, autoencoders can still form powerful building blocks for anomaly detection systems.

The shortcomings motivate a fundamentally different approach: prediction-based models, which learn to forecast the future based on the past. They better match the task of traffic forecasting. Recurrent and Transformer-based models can be easily extended to prediction-based models, as described in the following.

Prediction-Based Models and Probabilistic Regression

Prediction-based anomaly detection models learn to forecast the next value, or the next values, in a time series given past observations. These models not only provide a better understanding of temporal dependencies but also enable the detection of anomalies based on unexpected future behavior. Anomalies are detected by comparing the predicted output to the actual observation. The most basic variant uses a deterministic predictor, such as an LSTM, trained with a mean squared error (MSE) loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}} = \|x_{t+1} - \hat{x}_{t+1}\|^2, \quad (2.11)$$

where $\hat{x}_{t+1} = f_{\theta}(x_{t-k+1:t})$ is the predicted next value given the previous k observations, t is the current time step, and x_{t+1} is the actual next observation. While simple, it provides no notion of predictive uncertainty. In practice, this can lead to unreliable anomaly scores, especially in regions with high variance.

To address this, recent models adopt a probabilistic regression approach, where the network learns to output the parameters of a predictive distribution. A popular choice is the Gaussian likelihood:

$$x_{t+1} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_\theta(x_{t-k+1:t}), \Sigma_\theta(x_{t-k+1:t})). \quad (2.12)$$

The network predicts both the mean $\mu_\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and the positive definite covariance matrix $\Sigma_\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$. The model is trained by minimizing the negative log-likelihood (NLL) of the true next observation under the predicted Gaussian distribution:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NLL}}(x_{t+1}, \mu_\theta, \Sigma_\theta) = \frac{1}{2} \underbrace{\log |2\pi\Sigma_\theta|}_{\text{uncertainty penalty}} + \frac{1}{2} \underbrace{(x_{t+1} - \mu_\theta)^\top \Sigma_\theta^{-1} (x_{t+1} - \mu_\theta)}_{\text{Mahalanobis distance squared}} \quad (2.13)$$

The second term in the NLL loss is equivalent to the squared Mahalanobis distance between the true and predicted next value. The first term acts as a regularizer, penalizing large covariance estimates by encouraging moderate uncertainty. This formulation allows the model to learn both the expected value and the uncertainty of each dimension, as well as correlations between them. Anomaly scores are then computed based on the whole negative log-likelihood:

$$s(x_{t+1}) = -\log p_\theta(x_{t+1}|x_{t-k+1:t}) = \mathcal{L}_{\text{NLL}}(x_{t+1}, \mu_\theta, \Sigma_\theta), \quad (2.14)$$

where low likelihoods under the predicted distribution indicate anomalies. [MVSA15]

In some cases, the squared Mahalanobis term alone can be used as an anomaly score:

$$s(x_{t+1}) = (x_{t+1} - \mu_\theta)^\top \Sigma_\theta^{-1} (x_{t+1} - \mu_\theta), \quad (2.15)$$

as it directly measures the normalized deviation from the expected prediction. While this ignores the uncertainty regularization term in the full NLL, it can be advantageous for interpretability or when a more direct distance-based anomaly measure is desired.

This probabilistic prediction framework can be easily integrated as a head on top of different sequence encoders. For instance, convolutional networks (CNNs) can extract local temporal features, recurrent neural networks (RNNs) like LSTMs can capture long-range dependencies, and Transformer-based models can leverage global attention over input sequences. In each case, the final layer outputs the parameters of a multivariate Gaussian distribution, enabling uncertainty-aware anomaly scoring. The approach can be used in semi-supervised or unsupervised mode. In the semi-supervised case, only the normal data is used for training, leading to a more precise modeling of the usual data distribution.

Malhotra et al. [MVSA15] use the exact described framework with stacked LSTM networks for anomaly detection in time series. Other SOTA models adopt this framework by pairing probabilistic output heads with different backbone architectures. For example, DeepAR [SFGJ20] uses an autoregressive RNN to model time series and predict Gaussian parameters. The Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) [LALP21] extends this to multivariate settings, combining interpretable attention with probabilistic forecasting of percentile estimates. Other models, like OmniAnomaly [SZN⁺19], combine this multivariate probabilistic framework with the reconstruction-based approach. They use a

stochastic recurrent neural network and evaluate anomalies based on reconstruction probabilities, derived from a predicted multivariate Gaussian distribution. TranAD [TCJ22] combines a Transformer-based encoder with probabilistic reconstruction and prediction heads to model both expected behavior and deviations, enabling robust anomaly scoring in multivariate time series.

In summary, probabilistic prediction-based models combine forecasting and density estimation. They are well suited for applications like traffic anomaly detection, where the temporal context and prediction confidence are critical. Approaches specifically designed for anomaly detection in traffic scenes are discussed in Section 2.3. Moreover, many SOTA methods for sequence-based anomaly detection combine multiple frameworks, mostly reconstruction and forecasting, in a unified architecture. This design increases robustness and detection accuracy across complex temporal patterns. To fully assess the quality of such models, it is important to define how anomaly detection performance is measured.

2.1.4 Evaluation Metrics for Anomaly Detection

Defining suitable evaluation methods for evaluating anomaly detection methods is crucial for determining their effectiveness. The metrics should represent a methods' ability to find anomalies even though these anomalies are rare. We first present metrics commonly used for general anomaly detection and then describe a metric that is able to distinguish between different anomaly subclasses, assigning greater importance to the most significant anomalies during evaluation.

Precision, Recall, F1-Score, AU-ROC and AU-PR

Frequently used evaluation metrics include Precision, Recall, F1 Score, AU-PR and AU-ROC [ZDWP⁺24]. These metrics focus on performance concerning the rare positive class, the anomalies, rather than overall classification correctness. Other metrics, for example, the Accuracy, can be misleading in imbalanced scenarios. In the following, we define the metrics based on Zamanzadeh Darban et al. [ZDWP⁺24] and use the notations:

- TP for the amount of true positives - anomalies detected by the model,
- FP for the amount of false positives - normal data falsely classified as anomaly,
- TN for the amount of true negatives - normal data correctly classified as normal,
- FN for the amount of false negatives - anomalies the model has missed.

Precision Precision is the proportion of true positive results among all positive results predicted by the model:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}. \quad (2.16)$$

Low precision indicates many false alarms, because many normal samples have been classified as anomalies. High precision indicates most detected anomalies are actual

anomalies. The metric should be used when it is crucial to minimise false alarms and ensure that detected anomalies are truly significant.

Recall Recall is the proportion of true positive results among all actual positive cases:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}. \quad (2.17)$$

Low recall indicates many true anomalies are missed, leading to undetected critical events. High recall indicates most anomalies are detected. Use it when it is critical to detect all anomalies, even if it means tolerating some false alarms.

F1 Score The F1 Score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balance between the two metrics:

$$F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (2.18)$$

Low F1 score indicates poor balance between precision and recall, leading to either many missed anomalies or many false alarms. High F1 score indicates a good balance, ensuring reliable anomaly detection with minimal misses and false alarms. It is useful when both precision and recall are important, so reliable overall performance can be ensured.

Most anomaly detection techniques do not have a fixed boundary between the two classes, normal sample and anomalous sample, but rather produce a continuous output that indicates the degree of anomaly. Examples include distance measures like the Mahalanobis distance in future-predicting approaches and the reconstruction error in reconstruction-based approaches. In such cases, a threshold is chosen, and during inference, all outputs below the threshold are considered normal samples, while outputs above it are predicted as anomalies. Many evaluation metrics in anomaly detection include various thresholds in their calculation to assess model performance independently of any single threshold choice. The two prominent metrics are AU-ROC and AU-PR.

AU-ROC The Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (AU-ROC) represents the ability of the model to distinguish between normal and anomalous samples across all possible classification thresholds ϑ . The Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (ROC curve) plots the recall against the false positive rate at various threshold settings. The false positive rate is defined as:

$$\text{FPR} = \frac{FP}{FP + TN}. \quad (2.19)$$

The area under that curve is then defined as:

$$\text{AU-ROC} = \int_0^1 \text{Recall}(\vartheta) \frac{d(\text{FPR}(\vartheta))}{d\vartheta} d\vartheta. \quad (2.20)$$

A higher AU-ROC indicates better model performance. The metric is used for a general assessment of the model's ability to distinguish between normal and anomalous instances.

AU-PR The Area Under Precision-Recall Curve (AU-PR), also called Average Precision (AP), is, similar to AU-ROC, a measure of general model performance across all thresholds. It is particularly useful for imbalanced datasets because it focuses only on the performance with respect to the positive class. The Precision-Recall curve plots the precision against the recall, leading to the AU-PR defined as:

$$\text{AU-PR} = \int_0^1 \text{Precision}(t) \frac{d(\text{Recall}(t))}{dt} dt. \quad (2.21)$$

Low AU-PR indicates poor model performance, especially with imbalanced datasets. High AU-PR indicates strong performance, maintaining high precision and recall across thresholds. It is well-suited for most anomaly detection scenarios because anomalies are usually rare compared to normal instances.

Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (NDCG)

The Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (NDCG) is a ranking-based metric that is less commonly used in anomaly detection compared to AU-ROC and AU-PR. Nevertheless, it is mentioned in some anomaly detection surveys, including the work by Ekle and Eberle [EE24]. Given its ability to account for the varying importance of different anomalies, we argue that NDCG is an underutilized and very valuable metric for evaluating anomaly detection systems.

NDCG is used to evaluate the quality of a ranked list of items, often in the context of information retrieval or recommendation systems. The metric measures how well a ranking approach has performed in presenting the most relevant items at the top of the list. It considers the predicted scores and the items' relevance values. The predicted scores can, for example, be the Mahalanobis distances or reconstruction errors. The relevance values are typically real-valued and non-negative ground truth scores. Providing such relevance values enables the distinction between different anomaly subclasses, for instance, between highly significant anomalies and samples that may not be clearly perceived as anomalous by all observers. Since defining which scenarios are anomalies and which are not is a huge challenge in anomaly detection tasks, subcategories can be very beneficial.

Formally, let $\mathcal{D} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\}$ be the N items to rank. Let \mathcal{Y} be a finite set of degrees of relevancy. A simple case would be $\mathcal{Y} = \{0, 1, 2\}$, where 0 corresponds to false positive, 1 corresponds to a rather anomalous item, and 2 corresponds to a highly interesting anomaly. Generally \mathcal{Y} may contain more numbers, and for $y \in \mathcal{Y}$, the larger y is, the more relevance it represents. Let f be a ranking function, provided by an anomaly detection method. For each object $x \in \mathcal{D}$, f assigns a score $f(x) \in \mathbb{R}$. Let $x_{(1)}^f, \dots, x_{(N)}^f$ be the ranking list, satisfying $f(x_{(1)}^f) \geq \dots \geq f(x_{(N)}^f)$. y_1, \dots, y_n with $y_i \in \mathcal{Y}$ are the degrees of relevancy associated with x_1, \dots, x_n . Finally, let $y_{(1)}^f, \dots, y_{(N)}^f$ be the corresponding relevancy of $x_{(1)}^f, \dots, x_{(N)}^f$. [WWL⁺13]

The standard Discounted Cumulative Gain (DCG) is then:

$$\text{DCG}^{\text{lin}}(f, \mathcal{D}, \mathcal{Y}) = \sum_{r=1}^N \frac{y_{(r)}^f}{\log_2(1+r)}. \quad (2.22)$$

To give greater emphasis to items of high relevance, an exponential function is often applied to the relevance degrees in \mathcal{Y} :

$$\text{DCG}^{\text{exp}}(f, \mathcal{D}, \mathcal{Y}) = \sum_{r=1}^N \frac{2^{y_{(r)}^f} - 1}{\log_2(1 + r)}. \quad (2.23)$$

The Ideal DCG is the DCG value of the best ranking function and is defined as:

$$\text{IDCG}(\mathcal{D}, \mathcal{Y}) = \max_f \text{DCG}(f, \mathcal{D}, \mathcal{Y}), \quad (2.24)$$

leading to the NDCG of f :

$$\text{NDCG}(f, \mathcal{D}, \mathcal{Y}) = \frac{\text{DCG}(f, \mathcal{D}, \mathcal{Y})}{\text{IDCG}(\mathcal{D}, \mathcal{Y})} \quad (2.25)$$

The inverse logarithm $\frac{1}{\log_2(1+r)}$ in equation 2.23 is the standard discount function which ensures that the relevance of items appearing later in the ranking is weighted less. As a result, in the ideal ranking, items with the highest relevance scores are positioned at the top of the list. In many applications, a cut-off top- k version of NDCG is used. The discount is set to be 0 instead of $\frac{1}{\log_2(1+r)}$ for ranks r larger than k . Such an NDCG measure is usually referred to as NDCG@ k . [WWL⁺13]

While robust evaluation metrics like NDCG@ k are essential for assessing the quality of anomaly detection systems, their effectiveness depends on the quality of the underlying data representations. Most traffic anomaly detection methods operate not directly on raw video frames, but on structured representations such as trajectories of individual traffic agents. As a result, an important preliminary step in these applications is the detection and tracking of traffic agents.

2.2 Agent Detection and Tracking

In traffic anomaly detection, trying to reason directly and only from raw video frames quickly runs into problems: changing backgrounds, shifting light, occlusions, or even slight camera movement could be anomalies and hide the ones we really care about. Our targeted anomalies, like fast driving, near crashes and vehicles failing to yield, can be very subtle in comparison. By first detecting each vehicle, pedestrian or cyclist and then linking those detections, we extract clean, ID-preserving agent tracks from the video. From these tracks we can reliably compute things like speed changes, sudden stops, lane departures or unsafe gaps between vehicles—features that directly capture the behaviors we want to flag and aren’t hidden by pixel-level noise. Without that detection-and-tracking step, current trajectory-based anomaly models struggle to tell real incidents apart from random frame-to-frame distribution shifts.

At Starwit, we need a real-time and robust detection and tracking method for several Smart City projects. Therefore we adopt Ultralytics’ YOLOv8 [VM24] with its built-in tracker as the backbone of our detection and tracking pipeline. This architecture offers a practical balance between accuracy and efficiency, making it suitable

for large-scale traffic monitoring, while also providing the flexibility to integrate with anomaly detection models. In this section, we’ll lay out the combined challenge of multi-object detection and tracking and then introduce YOLOv8’s key architectural elements.

In a typical traffic surveillance scene, several agents move differently through the camera’s field of view. To analyze their behavior over time, each agent needs to be localized in every frame via bounding boxes and maintain a persistent identity. If a detector falsely misses a vehicle for a few frames, the resulting break in its track can be misinterpreted as an anomalous disappearance. Also, if two nearby agents swap IDs, the sudden change in the trajectory’s path may trigger false anomalies. Hence, in the context of traffic-anomaly detection, accurate object detection and consistent tracking IDs are fundamental. SOTA downstream trajectory analyzes and anomaly scores rely on precise tracks.

Formally, the detection task is, for each frame t , to produce a set of detections

$$D_t = \{\text{det}_{t,1}, \dots, \text{det}_{t,n_t}\}, \quad \text{det}_{t,i} = (b_{t,i}, \text{cl}_{t,i}), \quad (2.26)$$

where $b_{t,i} = (x_{\min}, y_{\min}, x_{\max}, y_{\max})$ is the bounding box and $\text{cl}_{t,i}$ is the class label. Multi-object tracking (MOT) then associates these detections with existing tracks $\{T_j^{t-1}\}$ by solving the task

$$\min_{a_{ij} \in \{0,1\}} \sum_{i,j} a_{ij} C(\text{det}_{t,i}, T_j^{t-1}) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \sum_j a_{ij} \leq 1 \quad \forall i, \quad \sum_i a_{ij} \leq 1 \quad \forall j, \quad (2.27)$$

where $a_{ij} = 1$ if detection $d_{t,i}$ is assigned to trajectory T_j . So each detection can only be assigned to one trajectory and each trajectory can only have one detection per time step t . $C(\cdot, \cdot)$ is a cost function including motion prediction and appearance similarity. A commonly used cost function is the Kalman filter [Kal60]. Unassigned detections start a new trajectory, and trajectories without matches for a certain number of frames are terminated.

Detectors nowadays can be divided into two categories: Two-stage and one-stage detectors. Two-stage detectors, like Faster R-CNN [RHGS15], first define regions of interest and then classify and change each proposal. These models have very accurate predictions but are often too slow for processing large video scenes with a high framerate. One-stage detectors, such as the YOLO models, predict object classes and bounding-box coordinates in a single run. They are slightly less precise, but much faster during inferencing. [AZ24]

You Only Look Once (YOLO) [RDGF16] simplifies the R-CNN approach a lot. The model divides the image into a small $S \times S$ grid, like 7×7 . A single CNN processes the entire image once and for each grid cell predicts the bounding boxes $b_{t,i}$ with a confidence score and the class probabilities conditioned on object presence. So a smaller task is done S^2 times. This divide and conquer approach only uses one single objective function. It consists of a localization part, for example MSE, for accurate bounding box predictions $(x_{\min}, y_{\min}, x_{\max}, y_{\max})$, a confidence part for object presence or absence, and a classification part for class label accuracy. The first version, YOLO v1, achieved >45 FPS on a GPU with this single-pass approach, which is fast enough for processing real-time video streams [RDGF16]. Since YOLO v1, performance improvements have been reached

Figure 2.3: YOLOv8-based detection and tracking process for a single frame.

by future versions through architecture fine-tuning, anchor boxes¹, multi-scale predictions from different feature maps and data-augmentation. The YOLOv8 [VM24] further added a CSP-based backbone to reduce redundancy and improve gradient flow, a decoupled head separating classification and regression for better localization, and an anchor-free option that directly predicts box centers and sizes without predefined priors. All these design choices maintain the core single-pass efficiency while pushing performance metrics scores higher, which is very important when processing multiple frames per second in a busy traffic scene. [AZ24]

YOLOv8’s tracking algorithm follows the tracking-by-detection paradigm with a simple two-stage matching scheme. The Kalman filter estimates each track’s future position and size based on the last observed bounding box and its velocity calculated from previous tracks in the trajectory. In the first stage, high-confidence detections are associated to existing tracks by maximizing the Intersection-over-Union (IoU) between the predicted box and each detection. In the second stage, the remaining detections with lower confidence are matched to any still unassigned tracks.

Figure 2.3 is an overview of YOLOv8’s detection and tracking process. Having YOLOv8’s ID-preserving trajectories additionally to video frames of traffic scenes forms a solid baseline to apply anomaly detection methods in this field.

2.3 Unsupervised Anomaly Detection in Traffic Scenes

In this section, we introduce recent unsupervised anomaly detection methods specifically designed for traffic scenes. In section 2.3.1, we present SOTA models for general traffic scenarios, and in section 2.3.2 we take a closer look at static overhead scenes, which are our application domain. We present their different characteristics as well as recent approaches for static overhead scenes.

¹Anchor boxes are predefined bounding boxes with certain sizes and aspect ratios that serve as starting points for the model’s predictions. They help the network to efficiently handle objects of different shapes and scales. [RHGS15]

2.3.1 SOTA unsupervised approaches for Traffic Scenes

Unsupervised anomaly detection in traffic scenes has been an active research area for over a decade, with initial video-surveillance studies appearing around 2010 [SDR20]. Early unsupervised traffic-anomaly systems in the late 2010s demonstrated feasibility on small road datasets. They mostly combined background modeling with rule-based tracking pipelines. Since 2020, interest has risen as multiple comprehensive surveys reflected a near doubled amount of research output in the past five years [SDR20]. The 2021 AI City Challenge winner Zhao et al. [ZWH⁺21] used a hand-crafted pipeline involving video stabilization, background modeling, and vehicle tracking to identify abnormal motion. While effective on small datasets, these methods struggle with scalability and generalization, highlighting the need for data-driven, end-to-end models. Thus, in the past three years, several end-to-end unsupervised frameworks have been developed and published in top-tier venues, like DoTA [YWX⁺23b], UMAD [BOJ⁺24] and uTRAND [DBDW24].

Recent approaches increasingly use self-supervised learning to generate pseudo-labels from the video data, mostly including object detection and tracking. The models outperform classical pipelines on standard benchmarks.

Future-Prediction and Reconstruction-Based Approaches Early deep learning solutions for unsupervised video anomaly detection model normal dynamics via prediction or reconstruction tasks as described in section 2.1.3. Liu et al. [LLG18] train a network to predict future frames and use prediction errors as anomaly scores. Approaches like that demonstrate that unusual events, like a crash, yield larger frame prediction errors than normal driving, but they struggle with anomalies that are nuanced and context-specific, for example, a stationary car in a pedestrian zone which is easy to predict. Gong et al. [GLL⁺19] point out that sometimes the deep learning models generalize so well that they can also reconstruct anomalies well, leading to the missed detection of anomalies. Hence, some reconstruction-based methods add mechanisms to prevent trivial learning of such rare but simple mappings. For instance, Gong et al. [GLL⁺19] introduced a Memory-augmented Autoencoder (MemAE) that stored prototypical normal patterns in the memory and uses them to constrain reconstruction of inputs. This forces the autoencoder to better reconstruct frequent normal events and leads to a poor reconstruction of the unusual events.

Anomalies in traffic are often understood as unusual motions or trajectories, such as a car driving on the wrong side or driving in wavy lines. For this reason, many SOTA methods build an explicit model of object trajectories in an unsupervised manner. Yao et al. [YWX⁺23b] developed an end-to-end framework focused on future trajectory prediction for driving videos. Their method predicts the short-term future locations of each detected traffic agent, including vehicles, pedestrians, and more. They then monitor the prediction consistency over time. An anomaly is signaled when the model’s predicted positions differ significantly or become inconsistent. This approach focuses on motion dynamics, making it more robust to camera motion. Yao et al. not only developed an anomaly detection method but also introduced the large-scale DoTA benchmark (Detection of Traffic Anomaly) [YWX⁺23a] with 4.677 videos of accidents and near-misses as illustrated in Figure 2.4. They provide spatial and temporal annotations for evaluation. On DoTA,

Figure 2.4: Example video frames from the DoTA dataset showing a collision anomaly (Source: [YWX⁺23a]).

their prediction-based anomaly detector outperformed earlier reconstruction and tracking pipelines. [YWX⁺23b]

Multi-Task Self-Supervised Learning Recent unsupervised traffic-anomaly detectors use multiple pretext tasks to learn rich, object-level representations without any manual labels. Georgescu et al. [GBI⁺21] introduced a 3D-CNN that jointly optimizes four self-supervised objectives on detected road agents, which are the discrimination of forward and backward moving objects, a motion-irregularity classification task, meaning the network has to distinguish between sequential and shuffled frames, an object appearance reconstruction task, and a normality distillation task. They achieved SOTA accuracy on multiple video anomaly benchmarks that mostly contain scenes of pedestrian avenues and plaza areas. Yu et al. [YWC⁺20] made use of the task Video Event Completion (VEC), a visual cloze test in which masked spatio-temporal cubes are reconstructed and their optical flow predicted. This further increased semantic sensitivity. To capture even more complex normal patterns, Liang et al. [LLY⁺23] proposed MAMTCF (Memory-Augmented Multi-Task Collaborative Framework), which combines optical flow reconstruction with future bounding box prediction.

Semantic and World-Model Approaches The most recent unsupervised techniques use a higher-level semantic understanding of traffic scenes. They often combine vision modules in a pseudo-labeling or generative fashion and are fundamentally future prediction-based approaches. For example, in 2024, Bogdoll et al. [BOJ⁺24] proposed UMAD (Unsupervised Mask-Level Anomaly Detection) that combines a generative world model to learn the normal appearance of the driving environment with unsupervised semantic segmentation. Their system builds a latent representation of the road scene by training on unlabeled sensor data. This representation includes the lanes, vehicles, and background, and is projected forward to predict expected observations. Anomalies are detected when the real sensor input, for example, the camera image, differs significantly from the predicted normal-world reconstruction. With this technique, UMAD easily detects where an anomaly appears. A fallen tree, for instance, will create a blob in the prediction error mask. This method achieved the best results compared to prior unsupervised detectors on driving datasets.

Another emerging group of approaches is the use of pre-trained foundation models. The techniques aim to recognize when an object or event in a traffic scene is conceptually novel, like an animal on the highway. They compare high-level features or textual descriptions of current and normal events.

In summary, recent unsupervised traffic anomaly methods have developed from hand-crafted models to end-to-end, data-driven frameworks that use self-supervised signals, like future motion prediction and pretext tasks, as well as structured scene representations like world models. The majority of these SOTA models focus on the use case of autonomous driving and they were developed for dashcam videos. In the following, we discuss the specific challenges of adapting these methods to static overhead scenes and then review approaches designed to address the unique characteristics of such scenes.

2.3.2 Characteristics of Static Overhead Scenes and Approaches

To address the problem of the scene domain shift, we highlight the fundamental data differences between dashcam videos and static overhead scenes. Dashcam datasets like DoTA [YWX⁺23a] feature anomalies prominently in the foreground that typically involve a single vehicle or a direct interaction, as shown in Figure 2.4. Static overhead scenes, on the other hand, offer the benefit of a stable camera perspective and a fixed road layout. This eliminates complexities through camera motion and allows for a stable understanding of the underlying infrastructure. However, these scenes have their own unique difficulties:

1. Numerous vehicles: Making individual object tracking and prediction more complex and allowing for anomalies in the interaction of multiple vehicles.
2. Upper-angled perspectives: Leading to smaller, less detailed vehicle appearances
3. Subtle anomalies: Where deviations might be minor (e.g., slightly off-course turns, unusual queuing patterns, failing to yield at one corner) or involve the interaction of several vehicles that are otherwise behaving normally.
4. Lack of dedicated datasets: There’s a general scarcity of publicly available benchmarks specifically designed for subtle anomalies in complex, fixed-camera intersection views. D’Amicantonio et al. collected a multi-camera intersection dataset and published it with their model uTRAND, which we review in the following.

The SOTA models presented in the previous section, particularly those evaluated on DoTA [YWX⁺23a] focus on detecting pronounced anomalies, like crashes. These techniques may not be optimally suited for the subtle, fine-grained anomalies often found in overhead camera scenes. Many approaches rely on reliable object detection and tracking, which can be challenging in crowded, high-angle camera views where objects might be small or occluded. Additionally, the majority of the presented approaches, like the future trajectory prediction by Yao et al. [YWX⁺23b], focus on individual vehicle trajectories, the point anomalies, and might miss anomalies arising from the interaction of multiple vehicles as well as subtle, collective deviations from typical traffic flow. UMAD [BOJ⁺24], on the other hand, works on the whole camera scene and thus is able to capture collective deviations, but its main components struggle with the domain shift of static overhead views in large, busy intersections. Their generative world model is trained on forward-facing, simulated driving data and might yield unstable reconstructions when vehicles appear at varied scales and angles. Additionally, unsupervised segmentation without further fine-tuning often fragments or misses small vehicles. Existing segmentation models

are mostly trained on frontal perspectives. Using such a pre-trained segmentation model under the significant domain shift of the overhead perspective will easily result in worse performance. All these small differences can lead to both false positives and missed anomalies.

To tackle these challenges, techniques specifically designed for fixed, static camera scenes have been developed recently. A promising direction are graph-based and trajectory-centric approaches. These methods excel at modeling vehicle interactions and typical routes, which is crucial for identifying anomalies in a dense traffic environment. In 2024, a particularly relevant method, uTRAND [DBDW24], was introduced by D’Amicantonio et al. It transforms static intersection video into a bird’s-eye-view, tracks agents, and builds a graph of normal routes and behaviors. Anomalies are then detected as deviations from this learned semantic-topological representation. This approach’s focus on semantic rules and statistical deviations in a graph space makes it highly suitable for identifying violations of traffic rules. Its interpretability is a significant advantage when analyzing complex intersection dynamics. On the other hand, uTRAND relies heavily on accurate detection and tracking of all traffic agents and their conversion to a bird’s-eye-view. In a dense, high-angle intersection view, objects can be small, occluded by other vehicles or infrastructure, and their detection and tracking quality can change significantly due to lighting, weather, or shadows. While an inaccurate bounding box for cars in the background is only a small mistake on the pixel level of the video frame, it will make a huge difference in terms of the vehicles’ position and size in the transformed bird’s-eye view. uTRANDs primary strength lies in detecting deviations from individual expected routes or behaviors. Anomalies such as a vehicle failing to yield can appear normal when considering individual trajectories in isolation. One car might slow down a bit and the other car proceeds normally even though it has to stop and give the first car the right of way. Detecting these cases with uTRAND therefore demands more sophisticated rule definitions and in-depth statistical analysis of agent interactions on the graph.

Another approach for static overhead scenes is LM-TAD (Language-Model-based Trajectory Anomaly Detection) [MPA24], introduced by Kabala Mbuya et al. in 2024, which treats vehicle trajectories as "sentences" and uses a Transformer to predict next positions. Unlikely routes are flagged as anomalies. While validated on GPS data, its idea of modeling sequential behavior is applicable to tracked traffic agents in static camera videos. The disadvantage is again the prerequisite of robust multi-object tracking, which can be difficult in dense, occluded intersection views. Detecting anomalies that arise collectively from multiple trajectories interacting together is also a major challenge for LM-TAD. LM-TAD focuses on the surprise score, the perplexity, of a single observed trajectory. It models the probability of a whole trajectory given its historical context, the previous locations. It would need significant modifications to explicitly model joint probabilities of multiple concurrent trajectories.

To demonstrate the importance of including context information and searching for collective anomalies, we provide two examples:

1. A car waiting at an intersection could be both normal and anomalous behavior depending on the context: If there are other cars passing by on the intersection it is completely normal for the car to wait and give them the right of way. However, it is unusual behavior to wait there for a long time if the intersection is fully empty and there are no traffic lights or other signs preventing the car from moving.

2. Similarly, a car standing several meters far from the intersection this would be unusual if the road is free. On the other hand, if other vehicles are already waiting at the intersection and the car just queues behind them this would be expected normal behavior.

Finally, we mention some methods that have been designed to capture collective interaction anomalies but, unfortunately, have other disadvantages that makes them unsuitable for our use case. An et al. [ALL⁺24] designed Spatio-Temporal Graph Normalizing Flows (STG-NF) that model the joint distribution of multi-agent trajectories to allow the detection of unlikely route combinations. However, their flow layers that include invertible transformations have high computational and memory costs that grow as vehicle counts grow, which we want to avoid in our Starwit anomaly detection method. Another promising technique are Interaction-Aware Trajectory Autoencoders, like the work from Wiederer et al. [WBT⁺21]. The AE learns a latent embedding of the entire traffic snapshot to detect anomalous group behaviors based on the reconstruction error, yet its tendency to average over common patterns can smooth out subtle deviations and might miss anomalies of single vehicles like a car driving too fast.

3 Methodology and Implementation

In this chapter, we begin by introducing the traffic-anomaly detection framework and its interface in Section 3.1. Section 3.2 then characterizes the data we use, followed by preprocessing steps in Section 3.3. In Section 3.4, we describe our early prototype explorations, introduce a nearest-neighbor baseline, and discuss shortcomings that motivate our final design. Finally, Section 3.5 presents our proposed probabilistic movement-forecasting model with insights into its implementation details.

3.1 System Overview

Our anomaly detection system is a component of the Starwit Awareness Engine (SAE) pipeline, a modular, end-to-end computer-vision pipeline. The SAE is designed to link together all core vision components under a single repository. The core components are video source, object detection, tracking, and data writers. The SAE provides a centralized entry point for documentation, configuration, and high-level orchestration code. It is easy to extend and monitor each stage of the vision workflow. Extensions provided by Starwit include a geospatial mapping (geo-mapper) to obtain a detection’s geo-coordinates and our anomaly detection module.

As highlighted in Chapter 2, state-of-the-art traffic anomaly detection systems usually include object detection and tracking outputs to precisely detect unusual behavior. Through the SAE, our anomaly detection component has direct access to the current YOLOv8 detections and their tracking information within a live video stream. The simplified process and the anomaly detector’s interface are illustrated in Figure 3.1.

We denote our anomaly system’s inputs at time step t as $\mathcal{T}_t = \{\text{tr}_{t,1}, \dots, \text{tr}_{t,n_t}\}$, meaning for each frame t we receive a set of all YOLOv8 agent detections and associated tracking IDs: $\text{tr}_{t,i} = (\text{det}_{t,i}, j)$. Here, $\text{det}_{t,i}$ is the agent detection and j the unique agent ID of the trajectory T_j to which this detection has been assigned. YOLOv8 returns all bounding-box coordinates scaled to the unit interval $[0, 1]$ in both x and y direction, with $(0, 0)$ located at the upper-left corner of the image. For a detailed explanation of the agent detection and tracking problem and our notation, see Section 2.2.

The anomaly detection component consists of a preprocessing stage, the core anomaly detection model that outputs anomaly scores $s_{t,j}$ for each track, and a postprocessing step that groups scores belonging to the same vehicle and computes a single score score_j for the whole trajectory T_j . We designed the per-detection anomaly scores to precisely localize anomalies. A score for each detection enables mapping the anomaly to a specific vehicle at a specific time. Computing a trajectory-level score is also important for analyzing a vehicle’s overall movement and identifying more extended anomalous behavior. For example, a movement with high anomaly scores $s_{t,j}$ collected over 5 seconds should yield

Figure 3.1: Schematic depiction of the Anomaly Detection System within the Starwit Awareness Engine (SAE) pipeline. The system receives detection and tracking data through the SAE, computes per-detection anomaly scores, and aggregates them into trajectory-level anomaly scores. If a trajectory’s score exceeds the threshold τ , it is flagged as anomalous.

a higher trajectory score than one with high scores lasting only one second. Finally, any trajectory j with $score_j > \tau$ is flagged as anomalous (see Equation 2.3). We select τ to match the user’s desired anomaly rate $a\%$. Specifically, τ is set to the $(100 - a)$ th percentile of all trajectory scores. By doing so, we ensure that only the top $a\%$ exceed the threshold.

In this setting, the anomaly detection (AnDe) stage learns the normal traffic behavior for each individual camera scene by first collecting the tracking data, and after sufficient observation, the model is fitted to the data’s distribution. After this training step, it predicts the anomaly scores as described and depicted in Figure 3.1.

The framework is designed so that the AnDe method and the trajectory-scoring algorithm can be easily replaced. Our main contribution is the movement-forecasting AnDe method, but before designing it, we developed a nearest-neighbor approach that also fits this framework. Common trajectory-scoring algorithms are matched with our AnDe models in Chapter 4 to select the best one and will not be covered further in this chapter. In our final Anomaly Detection System, we calculate a weighted average of all anomaly scores within each trajectory.

An important step before applying the anomaly detection system, is the calculation of a threshold τ for the trajectory anomaly scores, based on whom trajectories are flagged as anomalous or not, see Equation 2.3: x is an anomaly if $s(x) > \tau$. The threshold is chosen based on the percentual amount of anomalous trajectories a user wants to receive. Given that $a\%$ of all trajectories should be flagged as anomalous, the threshold is calculated such that it parts a set of trajectories such that the top $a\%$ trajectories with the highest trajectory anomaly scores are above the threshold.

3.2 Data Acquisition and Description

The traffic scenes we are working on are fixed surveillance camera views of areas with of high-traffic areas prone to anomalous behavior and car crashes, such as overhead views of intersections and roundabouts on major roads. The cameras are located in Carmel,

Figure 3.2: Example camera views of roundabouts and intersections in Carmel.

Indiana, USA, and capture high-resolution footage, up to 4 K. Figure 3.2 shows example scenes. Most scenes are large, two-lane roundabouts, but we also include intersections such as the pedestrian-area junction in Figure 3.2d. We have continuous access to these cameras, which is a powerful basis for observing and learning typical traffic-agent behavior.

In this environment, there are no limits on the amount of data. The anomaly detection does not require any human-made labels, and we can collect as much data as we need to fit the model. For training, we decided to gather the traffic-agent tracks over a 24-hour period.

We chose this time span for several reasons. First, fitting a distribution of normal behavior requires as many samples as possible. The more data we have, the closer its distribution resembles the true distribution. With too little data, machine-learning models tend to overfit, and any outliers in a small dataset may be mistakenly learned as normal behavior. The main reason for collecting exactly 24 hours is to ensure we capture traffic patterns from all day times, for instance high-traffic rush-hour scenarios, low-traffic periods, and even single-vehicle movement typical at night.

When the anomaly detection component starts on a video stream within the SAE, it first checks for existing AnDe model parameters. If they exist, the model is deployed with those parameters and is ready for inference (see Figure 3.1). If no parameters are found for that camera, data collection is triggered, and after 24 hours the model is fitted on the collected data. The new parameters are then stored, and anomaly detection begins.

For model evaluation, visualization, and selection, we use a second data-acquisition strategy. We run the SAE without the anomaly detector for 24 hours on a chosen camera and store each video frame t , downsampled to 320×180 , with its agent detections and tracks \mathcal{T}_t . This produces a fixed dataset on which multiple AnDe models can be trained and compared. Test datasets are extracted in the same manner.

Figure 3.3: Overview of the data preprocessing steps.

3.3 Data Preprocessing

In this section, we explain our data preprocessing pipeline, including trajectory smoothing and filtering. This is an important first step before performing traffic anomaly detection because small mistakes in a detector’s inputs are by definition anomalies, but they are anomalies in the observed tracking data rather than in the actual traffic scene. Thus, errors in agent detection and tracking lead to many false negatives for genuinely meaningful traffic anomalies. Common mistakes include imprecise bounding boxes or tracking-ID switches. Therefore, we implemented a preprocessing pipeline with multiple steps and strict filtering, making our anomaly detection applicable to agent detectors and trackers of varying quality.

Figure 3.3 shows an overview of the preprocessing steps. First, the raw agent detections \mathcal{T}_t , provided for each time step t , are grouped into trajectories T_j based on their associated tracking ID:

$$T_j = \bigcup_t \left\{ \text{tr}_{t,i} \in \mathcal{T}_t \mid \text{tr}_{t,i} = (\text{det}_{t,i}, j) \right\}. \quad (3.1)$$

Next, an optional filtering of parked vehicles follows. If an agent does not move for longer than a specified time threshold, detections after that threshold are removed. This step can be performed during model training to avoid the dominance of stationary vehicles in the training data. The training dataset is only used for learning the normal traffic behavior. Thus, if the AnDe model processes an input from only a single time step during each model run, we do not lose additional information by excluding time steps without movement. In this case, it makes sense to apply this preprocessing step to create a more informative training dataset and reduce training time.

Both our proposed model and baseline model operate this way. In our implementation, we use a threshold of 10 seconds, meaning the training set includes at most 10 seconds of stationary data from each parked vehicle. During inference, this preprocessing step should be omitted to ensure that an anomaly score is generated for every time step, which is crucial for accurately computing the overall trajectory anomaly score. For example, if a car stops for a long duration at an unusual location, each individual detection score will be high and should be included, clearly indicating anomalous behavior.

The three main components of the data preprocessing step are trajectory smoothing to correct inaccuracies in bounding boxes, motion extraction, and filtering out both individual tracks and entire trajectories that still contain errors. These steps are described in detail in the following sections.

3.3.1 Path Smoothing and Motion Extraction

Trajectory smoothing is performed to correct inaccuracies in bounding box positions and sizes caused by imprecise object detections. Each trajectory's bounding boxes are decomposed into minimum and maximum x and y coordinates. This step utilizes a median filter to smooth these coordinates: the lower-left corner (x_{\min}, y_{\min}) and the upper-right corner (x_{\max}, y_{\max}) . Median filtering effectively removes spikes and noise from data, especially impulsive noise which, for instance, can be the result of a bounding box "jumping" on a vehicle's shadow in one time step. The technique is easily interpretable and very suitable for real-time applications due to computational simplicity.

Formally, median filtering is defined as follows [ACD09]: given a one-dimensional discrete signal $X = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^N$ and a kernel size k , the median filtered output signal $Y = \{y_i\}_{i=1}^N$ is calculated as:

$$y_i = \text{median}(x_{i-\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_{i+\lfloor k/2 \rfloor}) \quad \forall i \in \{\lfloor k/2 \rfloor + 1, \dots, N - \lfloor k/2 \rfloor\}. \quad (3.2)$$

In our implementation, we use a median filter kernel size of seven. The bounding box coordinates are individually smoothed, and the smoothed coordinates are recomposed into new bounding boxes:

$$b_{\text{smooth}} = \left[(x_{\min}^{\text{smooth}}, y_{\min}^{\text{smooth}}), (x_{\max}^{\text{smooth}}, y_{\max}^{\text{smooth}}) \right]. \quad (3.3)$$

Note that the first and last $\lfloor k/2 \rfloor$ frames, referred to as border detections, are left unchanged, since the median filter kernel cannot be centered at the sequence boundaries.

Further, the centers $\{C_i\}_{i=1}^N$ of the smoothed bounding boxes are computed to provide stable object positions:

$$C_{\text{smooth}} = \left(\frac{x_{\min}^{\text{smooth}} + x_{\max}^{\text{smooth}}}{2}, \frac{y_{\min}^{\text{smooth}} + y_{\max}^{\text{smooth}}}{2} \right) \quad (3.4)$$

Following smoothing, we directly make use of the extracted bounding box centers to extract traffic agents' motion. To estimate the direction of movement for an object tracked over time, we apply a centered 7-frame sliding window and compute a robust line fit through the windowed positions. We aim for calculating the angle θ_t between the direction of movement and the x -axis, measured clockwise from the positive x -axis. Let

$$\{C_k\}_{k=t-3}^{t+3}, \quad C_k = (x_k, y_k) \quad (3.5)$$

be the pixel-normalized centers of the object from frame $t - 3$ to $t + 3$. We first check whether the total displacement Δ over the window exceeds a small threshold ε :

$$\Delta = \|C_{t+3} - C_{t-3}\|_2, \quad \Delta \geq \varepsilon \quad (\varepsilon = 0.015). \quad (3.6)$$

If $\Delta < \varepsilon$, the object is effectively stationary, and we propagate the previous angle θ_{t-1} . Otherwise, we fit the points $\{(x_k, y_k)\}$ to a line with a Theil-Sen regressor [The50, Sen68].

The regressor yields a slope m and intercept b by taking the median of all pairwise slopes, providing robustness against outliers. The fitted line is

$$y = m x + b. \quad (3.7)$$

We then evaluate this line at first and last window point to get a direction vector:

$$P_1 = (x_{t-3}, m x_{t-3} + b), \quad P_2 = (x_{t+3}, m x_{t+3} + b), \quad (3.8)$$

and form the displacement

$$\Delta_x = x_{P_1} - x_{P_2}, \quad \Delta_y = -(y_{P_1} - y_{P_2}). \quad (3.9)$$

Here we use the usual computer-vision convention in which the pixel origin $(0, 0)$ is at the upper-left corner and y increases downward. The minus sign flips the image-coordinate y axis so that it matches the standard mathematical convention with increasing Δ_y corresponding to upward motion.

Finally, the motion angle θ_t is computed using the two-argument arctangent:

$$\theta_t = (\text{atan2}(\Delta_y, \Delta_x) + 2\pi) \bmod 2\pi, \quad (3.10)$$

which directly leads to a θ_t measured clockwise from the positive x -axis. The arctangent (atan2) returns an angle in $(-\pi, \pi]$. Adding 2π and reducing $\bmod 2\pi$ converts it into $[0, 2\pi)$. This θ_t is assigned to the central detection t of the window, and for the border detections we replicate the nearest computed angle to ensure each detection has a defined motion direction.

Thus, these path smoothing and motion extraction steps reduce detector noise and enrich our trajectory information from Equation 3.1 with motion angles:

$$T'_j = \bigcup_t \left\{ \text{tr}'_{t,i} \in \mathcal{T}_t \mid \text{tr}'_{t,i} = (\text{det}_{t,i}, \theta_{t,i}, j) \right\}, \quad (3.11)$$

where $\text{det}_{t,i}$ now includes the smoothed bounding boxes and the object class label.

3.3.2 Selecting Reliable Vehicle Tracks for Anomaly Scoring

When aiming for the anomaly score of a certain vehicle, we still must address two issues that the median filter alone cannot resolve. These are missing detections within a trajectory (gaps), and identity switches where the tracker suddenly assigns a vehicle's object ID to a bypassing vehicle. Both of these errors can severely decrease the quality of downstream anomaly scores, so we apply an additional filtering strategy, where we prefer to discard ambiguous data rather than risk providing our model with noisy inputs.

Nevertheless, any tracks that we discard during this selection step may still contain valuable traffic scene information. For example, a trajectory whose id switched to another vehicle at some time step still includes correct object detections. Thus, all smoothed trajectories from the previous steps are not removed, some of them are just not selected for calculating anomaly scores.

First, we restrict the vehicles we want to consider for performing anomaly detection to cars, because in our SAE pipeline, car tracks are the most reliable. Thus, we only keep trajectories that are predominantly cars. We decided the detector must label a certain object as a car in at least 80% of its detections.

Next, we exclude parts of a trajectory in which the object does not appear in many video frames. The object should be included in at least 80% of the frames. We use a window in the form of a time interval sliding over the trajectories and checking how many tracks are missing in that interval. We use different lengths of the sliding window for our different AnDe models. More details about this follow later in this chapter.

Finally, to catch and remove identity-switch errors, we examine each object’s trajectory with a centered 5-frame sliding window and measure the change in direction. When the tracker jumps from one vehicle to another, it usually produces a sudden harsh movement change within the erroneous trajectory. Let C_t be the bounding box center of the object at time step t , and let $\theta(t, u) = |\theta(C_t, C_u)|$ be the angle between the direction of motion at time step t and u . At window position t , we compute four angle changes:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_1 &= \theta(t + 1, t) - \theta(t, t - 1), \\ \Delta_2 &= \theta(t + 2, t) - \theta(t, t - 2), \\ \Delta_3 &= \theta(t + 2, t) - \theta(t, t - 1), \\ \Delta_4 &= \theta(t + 1, t) - \theta(t, t - 2),\end{aligned}$$

where each Δ_k measures a different movement change between past and following tracks around the current time step t . If all Δ_k remain below a predefined threshold $\Delta\theta_{\max}$, which is set to $\frac{\pi}{3}$ ($= 60^\circ$) in our implementation, the motion is smooth and we mark the central track at t as *clear detection*. Otherwise, we assume a possible ID switch or spurious jump and skip ahead. Border detections are also marked as clear whenever their neighboring window passes the test, ensuring every valid segment contributes to downstream steps.

Only tracks marked as *clear detection* are later considered by the AnDe model for predicting an anomaly score. By enforcing this constraint, we only use trajectory segments with gradual, physically plausible turns, effectively filtering out abrupt, tracker-induced direction changes. This strict filtering ensures that our anomaly detection model is trained and evaluated on high-quality car tracks, reducing false anomalies due to detection artifacts.

3.4 Prototypes Explorations and Baseline Model

We tried several approaches for the core AnDe model of our anomaly detection pipeline before deciding on the movement forecaster. Our early approaches are briefly presented in this section. All of them served as meaningful baselines, motivating the design choices for our final approach. In particular, a nearest-neighbor-based method stood out in terms of performance. Consequently, we fully integrated it into the SAE as a baseline AnDe model for direct comparison in the evaluation in Chapter 4.

Figure 3.4: (a) Scatter of car-center points from the Rangeline Medical Drive camera, and (b) corresponding kernel density estimates where low-density regions (orange) indicate anomalies. Blue color indicates high density.

Figure 3.5: 2D slices of the 3D KDE at selected motion angles, showing the likelihood of vehicles driving in those directions at each position.

3.4.1 Early Prototypes and Design Drivers

When first faced with the traffic anomaly detection task, our initial goal was to find a method that works reasonably well for a limited set of anomalies. Later, we extended our scope to detect several types of anomalies.

First Approach: Kernel Density Estimation (KDE)

The motivation for anomaly detection arose from observing an accident in one camera feed: a driver, likely impaired, drove at high speed straight through the middle of a huge roundabout and crashed. Similar anomalies, such as a car driving on a pedestrian walkway, can be detected simply by learning the positions where vehicles normally appear. Therefore, we monitored the centers of all detected car bounding boxes, as shown in Figure 3.4a for the Rangeline Medical Drive camera.

We fit a distribution to these center points $\{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ using kernel density estimation (KDE) [Che17] with a 2-dimensional Gaussian kernel. Figure 3.4b visualizes the result. Areas with high probability density appear blue, fading to white as density decreases. The orange shading indicates that the region is flagged as anomalous, which happens whenever $f_{\text{KDE}}(x_j, y_j) < \gamma$ for an illustrative threshold γ . In practice, however, we do not

fix a single global threshold. Instead, for trajectory-level scoring we treat each detection’s negative density estimate as an individual anomaly score, and then aggregate these scores along a vehicle’s path.

This approach can be extended to include vehicle direction. In that case, the training set consists of 3-dimensional points $\{(x_i, y_i, \theta_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, allowing detection of unusual motion directions at given locations, such as wrong-way drivers. Because visualizing a 3D distribution is impractical, Figure 3.5 shows two-dimensional slices of the KDE at selected angles θ_i . Each image shows where driving in the certain direction is likely.

Since computing the KDE at runtime for every detection is too expensive, we precompute density values on a uniform grid over $(0, 1) \times (0, 1) \times (0, 1]$, where the last dimension corresponds to motion angle normalized to $(0, 1]$. At inference, each observed point $(x_i^*, y_i^*, \theta_i^*)$ is assigned the density of its nearest grid point.

While this method can detect wrong-way drivers, there were many detections with very low densities that we would not consider truly interesting anomalies, for example, vehicles moving in parking lots. Such movements are naturally less frequent and more directionally varied, yielding low densities across all angles. Therefore, we needed an approach that does not model the entire distribution, but rather focuses on the parts relevant to each detection and requires much less computation. We thus developed a nearest-neighbor-based technique that concentrates on local neighborhoods and similarly detects anomalies based on a vehicle’s position and motion angle, which is explained in Section 3.4.2.

Sequential Approach: LSTM Autoencoder

Since we are interested in detecting all kinds of traffic anomalies, we need methods capable of capturing complex movement patterns. Many state-of-the-art (SOTA) trajectory-based approaches learn a vehicle’s typical behavior directly from its full trajectory, inferring features such as turns, motion direction, and speed without hand-crafted preprocessing. Hence, we implemented an LSTM autoencoder [MRA⁺16], a common method for sequential anomaly detection (see Section 2.1.3).

We trained our LSTM autoencoder to reconstruct segments of each trajectory. We sampled each car’s positions at ten equally spaced time steps to form the model’s input and reconstruction target. However, after training, the model rarely flagged truly interesting anomalies. Most of its high reconstruction errors corresponded to normal turning at intersections.

Gong et al. [GLL⁺19] explain this phenomenon: although a deep autoencoder is trained on normal data and is expected to yield larger reconstruction errors on abnormal inputs, it can sometimes generalize well enough to reconstruct anomalies accurately, causing them to be missed. In trajectory anomaly detection, a model that generalizes too well might easily reconstruct a vehicle driving straight but excessively fast. Reconstructing a straight trajectory line can be very easy, leading to overlooking the speed anomaly. Likewise, an LSTM autoencoder might reconstruct a wrong-way driver’s straight path successfully. Moreover, the LSTM struggled to capture fine-grained spatial relationships and temporal dependencies across multiple agents, since it treats each trajectory in isolation.

Therefore, we decided not to pursue reconstruction-based anomaly detection further. We concluded that, for our final approach, the movement forecaster, it is more important to incorporate scene context than to rely on long individual trajectory histories. From our prototypes, we infer that an agent’s expected behavior at any moment depends more on the surrounding traffic than on its path several seconds earlier. By including nearby agents, we can detect interactions such as cutting off or failing to yield.

3.4.2 A Nearest Neighbor Baseline for Comparison

Inspired by the challenges faced with our initial KDE method, we implemented a nearest neighbor (NN)-based anomaly detection baseline. This approach is particularly suited for scenarios where anomalies are characterized by deviations from locally typical vehicle movements, thus leveraging the assumption common to NN techniques: normal instances are located within dense neighborhoods, whereas anomalies appear isolated or in sparse areas [CBK09]. Our goal was to capture subtle deviations in motion direction or position efficiently and robustly, without the computational overhead of continuous density estimation.

Our technique builds a model of local normal vehicle movements over the scene, then scores new detections by their deviation from this model. During model construction, we discretize the spatial domain, gather local orientation statistics, and cluster similar headings. Following, in anomaly scoring, each new detection is assigned a z-score against its local distribution.

Model Construction

We first construct our model to represent normal vehicle movements. Given a training set of all vehicle trajectories $\{T'_j\}$, containing detections enriched with motion angles θ . We first collect the centers of the bounding boxes as spatial coordinates in a set $X = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ as well as the corresponding angles $\Theta = \{\theta_i\}_{i=1}^N$. To efficiently model local behavior, we discretize the normalized image plane $[0, 1] \times [0, 1]$ into an $M_x \times M_y$ regular spatial grid. For each grid cell (i, j) , centered at coordinates (x_{ij}, y_{ij}) , we identify the neighborhood of points within a radius ϵ :

$$\mathcal{N}_{ij} = \{k : |(x_k, y_k) - (x_{ij}, y_{ij})|_2 < \epsilon\} \quad (3.12)$$

Next, we convert each neighbor’s motion angle into a 2-dimensional vector $(\cos \theta_k, \sin \theta_k)$, where $k \in \mathcal{N}_{ij}$. By doing so, we embed the circular nature of motion angles into a continuous Euclidean space, which avoids the discontinuity at $0/2\pi$ and enables meaningful distance computations.

We then apply density-based clustering (DBSCAN) [EKSX96] on the data points in the neighborhood \mathcal{N}_{ij} individually for each grid cell (i, j) . We define the DBSCAN radius for the motion angles ϵ_θ and minimum cluster size minPts to capture dominant traffic directions robustly. Each resulting cluster c yields a mean direction $\bar{\theta}$ and an angular standard deviation σ_θ . For cell (i, j) , we store the lists $\{\bar{\theta}_{ij,c}\}_{c=1}^{\mathcal{C}_{ij}}$ and $\{\sigma_{ij,c}\}_{c=1}^{\mathcal{C}_{ij}}$, where \mathcal{C}_{ij} is the number of clusters found. Thus, the motion statistics are fully precomputed and the model can be used offline.

Figure 3.6: Visualization of the nearest neighbor-based clustering approach on the Rangeline Medical Drive camera, showing (a) the spatial map of local motion statistics and (b) a close-up of the region marked in (a). Each blue triangle’s orientation shows the mean heading $\bar{\theta}_{ij,c}$ in its grid cell, and its width represents the angular spread $\sigma_{ij,c}$.

Figure 3.6 visualizes the typical motion directions for each grid cell. To reveal finer details, Figure 3.6b shows a zoomed-in section of the scene. Each small blue triangle represents a cluster. Its mean direction $\bar{\theta}_{ij,c}$ is indicated by the triangle’s orientation relative to the grid point, and its width corresponds to the cluster’s standard deviation $\sigma_{ij,c}$. In areas where vehicles turn following the curve of the roundabout, the standard deviations are noticeably larger, whereas in areas where two streets intersect, such as on the left side of Figure 3.6b, there are two clusters representing the two main directions.

Anomaly Scoring

At inference time, each new detection at (x^*, y^*, θ^*) is first mapped to its grid cell (i^*, j^*) . We look up the precomputed cluster statistics $(\{\theta_c\}, \{\sigma_c\})$ for cell (i^*, j^*) . We then distinguish two cases: the cell either contains precomputed cluster statistics or is empty. For notational simplicity, we drop the (i^*, j^*) subscripts and write $\bar{\theta}_c$ instead of $\bar{\theta}_{i^*j^*,c}$ and σ_c instead of $\sigma_{i^*j^*,c}$.

Nonempty cell If the cell contains one or more clusters, we compute the angular deviation for each cluster c :

$$\Delta\theta_c = \min(|\theta^* - \bar{\theta}_c|, 2\pi - |\theta^* - \bar{\theta}_c|) \quad (3.13)$$

and the corresponding z-score [Woo13]:

$$z_c = \frac{\Delta\theta_c}{\sigma_c} \quad (3.14)$$

The z-score measures how many standard deviations the observed motion direction deviates from the cluster mean, so it normalizes deviations by the cluster’s angular spread.

The anomaly score for the detection is the minimum z-score across all local clusters:

$$z = \min_{c \in \mathcal{C}} z_c. \quad (3.15)$$

A low z means the heading closely matches one of the local clusters and a high z indicates an unusual direction.

Empty cell If the cell has no clusters, which indicates that vehicles are normally not observed at that position. Detections falling in such areas are clearly anomalous. Recall the example of a car driving on a pedestrian walkway. We treat the position itself as anomalous and search for the nearest grid cell (i', j') that does have clusters. Let d be the Euclidean distance (in cell-units) between (i^*, j^*) and (i', j') . We then compute

$$z = 100 + \left(\min_c (\Delta\theta'_c / \sigma'_c) \right) \times (d + 1), \quad (3.16)$$

so that detections outside any known traffic region automatically receive a very high base score of 100 and are further increased by both their heading deviation and their distance to the nearest valid region.

These anomaly scores per detection can be further aggregated to trajectory scores, which is analyzed in Chapter 4. In conclusion, this nearest-neighbor baseline is computationally efficient, directly interpretable, and capable of detecting localized anomalies in vehicles’ motion direction without making assumptions about traffic patterns.

3.4.3 Nearest Neighbor Implementation Details and Parameters

This section describes the implementation details and parameter settings of our nearest-neighbor AnDe model. As mentioned in Section 3.3.2, we restrict anomaly detection to cars, since different vehicle types, for instance, busses and bicycles, and also pedestrians follow distinct trajectories and would require separate models. Focusing on a single category ensures that the neighborhood analysis captures only the relevant movement patterns and does not include other vehicle’s specific path variations.

In preprocessing, as explained in Section 3.3.2, we exclude any trajectory segments where the agent was detected in fewer than 80% of frames. Here, we apply a sliding window of length 0.5 s to ensure each data sample is directly flanked by neighboring detections, so we assume a high quality of the calculated motion angles. Since we do not model long-term dependencies, a short interval suffices. Additionally, because this model targets moving agents, we discard detections whose displacement from the previous valid point is below 0.005 units, as these represent negligible or noisy motion, such as cars stopping at intersections.

For the core model, we selected practical parameter values:

- Grid discretization ($M_x \times M_y$): We use a step size of 0.0025 in both the x and y dimensions, yielding a 400×400 grid. This resolution balances spatial precision against computational cost, which scales as $O(M_x \cdot M_y)$. To process the entire grid

efficiently, we parallelize column-wise computations using a work-stealing thread pool, that ensures high CPU utilization even when column workloads vary.

- Neighborhood radius (ϵ): Set to 2% of the image dimension ($\epsilon = 0.02$). A perspective-dependent radius might better reflect real-world distances. But since the nearest neighbor approach is not able to capture all our desired anomaly types, we did not further invest time into such subtle improvements.
- DBSCAN angular radius (ϵ_θ): $\frac{\pi}{12}$ ($= 15^\circ$), so that groups of motion angles differing by more than $\frac{\pi}{12}$ cannot belong to the same cluster.
- DBSCAN minPts: This parameter specifies the minimum number of points required to form a cluster. We set $\text{minPts} = \max(0.005 \cdot |\mathcal{N}_{ij}|, 10)$, a grid-cell-dependent threshold that ensures each cluster covers at least 0.5% of the motion angles of all neighbors in cell (i, j) , while enforcing a minimum of 10 points. We did not choose a fixed threshold as we do not want to strictly exclude motions in areas with less cars.

The model shown in Figure 3.6 was computed using these settings. After offline computation, we serialize the model to JSON as a list of length $M_x \times M_y$. Each entry contains two arrays of length $|\mathcal{C}_{ij}|$: $\{\bar{\theta}_{ij,c}\}_{c=1}^{\mathcal{C}_{ij}}$ and $\{\sigma_{ij,c}\}_{c=1}^{\mathcal{C}_{ij}}$. Cells without clusters have empty arrays. This storage enables fast and direct lookup during inference.

3.5 Final Approach: Probabilistic Movement Forecasting

This section introduces our proposed AnDe model, the probabilistic movement forecaster (PMF). We begin with a system overview and then describe the framework in detail. Following that, we provide implementation details. All illustrative figures in this section stem from the Rangeline Medical Drive camera scene (see Figure 3.2a).

3.5.1 Overall Model Architecture

The proposed movement forecasting (PMF) model aims to detect anomalies by predicting the future positions of vehicles based on the surrounding traffic context rather than relying only on individual vehicle trajectories. Figure 3.7 presents a schematic overview of the method. It is a deep learning anomaly detection approach based on a convolutional neural network (CNN) backbone.

Our approach begins by processing the smoothed trajectories obtained through our pre-processing explained in Section 3.3. At each time step t , the target vehicle j , whose anomaly score we wish to calculate, is identified. Additionally, we gather contextual information from surrounding traffic agents like other vehicles, bikes, and pedestrians present at the same time step. Both the target vehicle and context agents are represented through their bounding boxes (bboxes) and motion angles, forming a 2-dimensional input.

This 2-dimensional scene representation allows a CNN to easily interpret a vehicle’s location and to effectively learn the spatial relationships as well as typical driving patterns in a scene’s different locations. CNNs, introduced by Fukushima [Fuk80], analyze local

Figure 3.7: Schematic depiction of the probabilistic movement forecaster.

spatial context, and their hierarchical feature extraction captures multi-scale interactions among vehicles. Both properties are especially advantageous for modeling complex traffic scenes. In our approach, any convolutional model architecture can be used as a backbone.

In the PMF, the CNN performs probabilistic regression to predict the target vehicle’s near-future position δ seconds ahead, typically only very few seconds like 0.5 or 2 seconds. It outputs parameters of a bivariate Gaussian distribution, specifically the mean expected position $\hat{C}_{t+\delta,j}$ and its associated covariance $\Sigma_{t+\delta,j}$.

Finally, the Mahalanobis distance between the predicted distribution and the actual future position $C_{t+\delta,j}$, which we extract from the target vehicle’s trajectory, is computed, yielding the anomaly score:

$$s_{t,j} = D_M(C_{t+\delta,j}; \hat{C}_{t+\delta,j}, \Sigma_{t+\delta,j}). \quad (3.17)$$

A large distance indicates that the observed vehicle position significantly deviates from the expected behavior, thus marking it as anomalous.

Details on the PMF’s system design, the model training and loss-function, as well as our implementation are described in the following sections.

3.5.2 Input-Output Design and Ground Truth Generation

In our proposed Probabilistic Movement Forecasting (PMF) framework, the input preparation and design of the input channels are crucial to capture the essential contextual information while excluding irrelevant variations. The main objective is to allow the model to effectively infer future vehicle positions from spatial context and interaction patterns, rather than relying on easily predictable cues such as vehicle speed or environmental lighting conditions.

Figure 3.8: Visualization of the model input. (a) Simplified input, showing the bounding boxes of all traffic agents. The target vehicle is highlighted in blue. The gray background depicts the full scene for interpretability only. (b) Actual input, consisting of four 2D masks that encode the sine and cosine of the motion angles in the context and target vehicles’ bounding boxes.

Input Channel Design

The input to our CNN consists of a four-channel representation derived from the bounding boxes and motion angles of the vehicles. The bounding boxes provide a compact and straightforward spatial representation of vehicles, facilitating efficient model training without unnecessary background distractions such as weather conditions or varying lighting during day and night. The whole scene image as depicted in the illustrations in Figure 3.7 and Figure 3.8a is just added for better reader interpretability. By focusing only on simplified representations, as shown in Figure 3.8b, our model can effectively capture subtle and essential interactions, implicitly learning traffic rules independent of environmental factors.

To encode orientation without revealing exact directional information, each vehicle’s movement angle θ should be treated as undirected: $\theta \in [0, \pi)$ instead of $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$. This prevents the model from directly inferring absolute travel direction and instead forces it to learn typical motion patterns from spatial context. Such abstraction is crucial when detecting anomalies such as wrong-way driving. If the direction were provided explicitly, the model could simply forecast an anomalous trajectory rather than flagging it as unusual. To achieve this, the orientation is represented in a doubled-angle sine–cosine embedding:

$$\text{channel}_{\sin} = \sin(2\theta), \quad \text{channel}_{\cos} = \cos(2\theta). \quad (3.18)$$

This encoding captures the cyclic nature of angular data and ensures continuity at the boundary, so that angles near 0 ($= 0^\circ$) and near π ($= 180^\circ$) map to numerically close values. The encoding is undirected since θ and $\theta + \pi$ yield the same representations.

As visualized in Figure 3.8b, each bounding box and motion angle pair is transformed onto a 2-dimensional input mask with two channels, one for the sine and one for the cosine values, that are placed inside the bounding boxes. As a result, the CNN has four input channels. Two channels include the context vehicles and two channels mark the target vehicle. This clear separation ensures that the CNN can distinctly learn the interaction of context vehicles with the target vehicle.

Exclusion of Additional Details in the Input

Several potential input features, such as vehicles' past positions and environmental background like daytime and weather conditions, were intentionally excluded.

Weather conditions and lighting variations do not influence inherent traffic rules or vehicle interaction patterns. By omitting these factors, the model avoids unnecessary complexity and distractions, focusing instead on learning the critical and complex interactions among vehicles.

Additionally, the model should not rely on vehicles' past trajectory part. If past positions are provided to the model, it could easily infer the current vehicle's speed and use this feature to predict future positions. If speed were included, anomalies such as speeding or abnormally slow vehicles could go undetected, as the model would correctly predict their future positions simply based on their current velocities. By not providing past positions, the model is forced to learn typical velocities from contextual clues and spatial arrangements. Deviations, such as unusually fast or slow driving, can then be detected through observing significant deviations between predicted and actual future positions.

While not included in the PMF framework described here, adding object class labels as an additional input channel seems reasonable. This would allow the CNN to learn specific behaviors of different vehicle or object types, which can be useful when aiming at finding anomalies across several types of traffic agents. Another possibility is training a separate model for each agent type of interest.

Ground Truth Generation

Ground truth future positions, required for training and evaluating the probabilistic regression as well as for calculating the anomaly score, are computed through linear interpolation. Given timestamps and bounding-box center positions of the target vehicle's trajectory T'_j , we interpolate the vehicle's location at exactly δ seconds into the future, to receive a precise target position even if the track $\text{tr}_{t+\delta,j}$ is not directly included in T'_j . If there is no time step $t' > t + \delta$ in T'_j , we omit the current track as the vehicle has left the scene around time $t + \delta$.

Probabilistic Output Modeling

The PMF model performs probabilistic regression. In the basic case, it outputs parameters of a predicted bivariate Gaussian distribution, which are the mean predicted position $\hat{C}_{t+\delta,j}$ and the covariance matrix $\Sigma_{t+\delta,j}$. The predicted mean represents the

expected future position, while the covariance indicates uncertainty and directional variability.

In detail, the model’s probabilistic regression head consists of three linear layers. The mean layer directly outputs the x and y -coordinate of $\hat{C}_{t+\delta,j}$. The 2×2 covariance matrix is not directly predicted, due to correlations between its entries. We use a layer that produces the coordinates’ individual log-variances $[\log \sigma_x^2, \log \sigma_y^2]$. We predict log-variance rather than variance directly to enforce positivity and numerical stability during optimization. The last layer computes the correlation value ρ bounded to $(-1, 1)$ through tanh activation. These outputs form the covariance matrix [HT75]:

$$\Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x^2 & \rho\sigma_x\sigma_y \\ \rho\sigma_x\sigma_y & \sigma_y^2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.19)$$

Because $\theta_x, \theta_y > 0$ and $|\rho| < 1$, the matrix Σ is guaranteed to be symmetric and positive definite, ensuring that its inverse is well defined. This modular design thus yields a valid Gaussian distribution and decouples feature extraction from probabilistic parameter prediction, letting the backbone CNN proceed independently of the Gaussian-head logic.

Finally, the Mahalanobis distance $D_M(C_{t+\delta,j}; \hat{C}_{t+\delta,j}, \Sigma_{t+\delta,j})$ (see Equation 2.5) between the predicted Gaussian distribution and the actual future position is used as an indicator for anomalous movement and directly interpreted as the tracks $tr_{t,j}$ anomaly score $s_{t,j}$:

$$D_M(C_{t+\delta,j}; \hat{C}_{t+\delta,j}, \Sigma_{t+\delta,j}) = \sqrt{(C_{t+\delta,j} - \hat{C}_{t+\delta,j})^\top \Sigma_{t+\delta,j}^{-1} (C_{t+\delta,j} - \hat{C}_{t+\delta,j})}. \quad (3.20)$$

In the following, we refer to this typical Mahalanobis distance measure as $D_{M,\text{sym}}$.

Extension to Asymmetric Mahalanobis Distance

In the extended model version, we introduce an additional tanh-output layer predicting skew parameters λ_x and λ_y to model directional asymmetry in the predicted distribution. This extension is inspired by the concept of skewed loss functions introduced by Wang et al. [WTM⁺23]. Wang et al. originally introduced the skewed loss function in a one-dimensional context, where a step function scales the loss \mathcal{L} asymmetrically depending on the sign of the prediction error. Specifically, let ϵ be the prediction error, they define the skew factor s as:

$$s(\epsilon) = e^{\text{sgn}(\epsilon)\lambda}, \quad (3.21)$$

leading to the scaled loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{skewed}}(y, \hat{y}) = \mathcal{L}(y, \hat{y})s(y - \hat{y})$ between ground truth label y and predicted value \hat{y} .

In our approach, we adapt this concept to two dimensions and apply it during the computation of the Mahalanobis distance. We introduce two learnable skew parameters, λ_x and λ_y , to account for direction-specific asymmetry in uncertainties along both axes. Unlike [WTM⁺23], our skew parameters are trainable and allow the model to dynamically adjust the skew based on observed data.

(a) Ground truth position $C_{t+\delta,j}$ shown in the scene.

(b) Probabilistic regression outputs $\hat{C}_{t+\delta,j}$ and $\Sigma_{t+\delta,j}$ of a (symmetrical) Gaussian Distribution.

(c) Skewed Mahalanobis boundary with points of equal distance given $\Sigma_{t+\delta,j}$ and skew parameters $\lambda_{t+\delta,j}$.

Figure 3.9: Visualizations of (a) the ground truth position $C_{t+\delta,j}$ of target vehicle j in the blue bounding box $\delta = 1$ second ahead, (b) the corresponding symmetric probabilistic regression outputs and (c) the asymmetric distribution with the skew applied in the Mahalanobis distance D_M .

The error vector $\epsilon_{t+\delta,j} = C_{t+\delta,j} - \hat{C}_{t+\delta,j}$ utilized in our original Mahalanobis distance calculation in Equation 3.20 is now replaced as follows:

$$\epsilon_{t+\delta,j}^{(\text{skewed})} = (C_{t+\delta,j} - \hat{C}_{t+\delta,j}) \odot e^{\text{sgn}(C_{t+\delta,j} - \hat{C}_{t+\delta,j}) \odot \lambda_{t+\delta,j}}, \quad (3.22)$$

where $\lambda_{t+\delta,j} = [\lambda_{t+\delta,j;x}, \lambda_{t+\delta,j;y}]$ are the predicted skew parameters and \odot is element-wise multiplication. Thus, our asymmetrical Mahalanobis distance is defined as:

$$D_{M,\text{asym}}(C_{t+\delta,j}; \hat{C}_{t+\delta,j}, \Sigma_{t+\delta,j}, \lambda_{t+\delta,j}) = \sqrt{\epsilon_{t+\delta,j}^{(\text{skewed})\top} \Sigma_{t+\delta,j}^{-1} \epsilon_{t+\delta,j}^{(\text{skewed})}}. \quad (3.23)$$

This modification enhances the model's ability to capture subtle directional deviations by removing the restriction that the predicted distribution of a future position must be symmetrical. Examples of our two different predicted distributions are visualized in Figure 3.9. The asymmetric distributions in Figure 3.9c fit slightly better, as they incorporate perspective and uncertainty in possible direction changes. The first and last images show that, based on perspective, the mean is closer to the Mahalanobis boundary that is farther

from the camera, since there is less uncertainty in motion at greater distances because vehicles move more slowly in pixel space. The second and third images show uncertainty about the target vehicle changing direction at the intersection. The CNN learns to widen the distribution on the side away from the vehicle.

3.5.3 Training Objective and Loss Formulation

Training the PMF model optimizes a negative log-likelihood (NLL) term derived from the Mahalanobis distance. This encourages accurate prediction of both mean positions and uncertainty estimates through the covariance matrix and, in the asymmetric case, the skew parameter. Our NLL loss includes some method-specific adaptations from the standard NLL loss, which this section highlights.

Recall the general NLL loss \mathcal{L}_{NLL} for probabilistic regression in Equation 2.13. Applied to our symmetric output \hat{C} and Σ , with ground truth future position C , we obtain

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NLL}}(C, \hat{C}, \Sigma) = \frac{1}{2} \underbrace{\log |2\pi\Sigma|}_{\text{uncertainty penalty}} + \frac{1}{2} \underbrace{(C - \hat{C})^\top \Sigma^{-1} (C - \hat{C})}_{\text{Mahalanobis distance squared}}. \quad (3.24)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NLL}} = D_M^2 + \underbrace{\log |2\pi\Sigma|}_{\text{uncertainty penalty}} \quad (3.25)$$

We omit the indices $t + \delta, j$ here for simplicity. The second term in the NLL loss is the squared Mahalanobis distance $D_{M, \text{sym}}^2$. The first term acts as a regularizer, penalizing large covariance estimates by encouraging moderate uncertainty. However, since the determinant penalty $|\Sigma|$ multiplies the coordinates' individual variances and their correlation, it can be minimized by shrinking one variance axis arbitrarily while inflating the other. This imbalance can cause one dimension to collapse, meaning it has a very small variance, and the other to stretch excessively. We observed this behavior during training. The covariance ellipses became highly elongated. Therefore, we decided to penalize the trace of Σ instead of its determinant to only constrain the sum of variances along both axes and more effectively prevent overly thin ellipses. We also omit the $\frac{1}{2}$ factor since constants do not affect gradients. The full loss function is shown at the end of this section.

We further observed that during batch-wise training, since the model is updated based on the mean loss across all samples in a batch, the trace of individual Σ matrices became similar. This behavior is unintended, as pixel-level motion varies significantly across different regions of the input image, and the uncertainty should vary accordingly. In the camera scene shown in Figure 3.9, vehicles in the lower half of the image move much faster than those in the upper half, which contains vehicles at a greater distance. Hence, we include a scaling factor based on object distance in our loss function.

We first compute a camera-perspective mapping by fitting a linear regression model between bounding-box size and the image's row coordinate:

$$\text{slope, intercept} = \text{LinearRegression}(C_y \mapsto \alpha), \quad \alpha = w + h,$$

where C_y is the bounding-box center's row coordinate, and w and h are its width and height, respectively. Here we assume a linear relation between the image's y -coordinate

and bounding-box size, which is not entirely accurate due to camera curvature and other factors. The approximately linear relationship arises from perspective projection: objects farther from the camera project to smaller bounding boxes, and in a fixed-height camera setup, scene depth increases approximately linearly with the vertical coordinate y [Zha00]. Over the limited depth range of typical traffic scenes, this simple approximation suffices for our scaling.

At training time, each sample’s vertical image coordinate $C_{y,j}$, taken from the ground truth future position, yields the approximate vehicle size α_j in pixel units:

$$\alpha_j = \text{slope} \cdot C_{y,j} + \text{intercept}. \quad (3.26)$$

We normalize and invert this value to get a penalty factor $\tilde{\alpha}$ that favors greater regularization for small, distant objects:

$$\tilde{\alpha}_j = \frac{\max_i \alpha_i - \alpha_j}{\max_i \alpha_i} + 0.1, \quad (3.27)$$

where α_i is the largest bounding-box size within the current batch, and 0.1 is added to prevent $\tilde{\alpha}_j$ from becoming zero and to set a minimum penalty factor. The covariance regularizer is then

$$\mathcal{R}(\Sigma, C) = \tilde{\alpha}_j \cdot \log(1 + \text{trace}(\Sigma)), \quad (3.28)$$

where 1 is added to the trace for numerical stability. This formulation enforces tighter uncertainty bounds for distant vehicles with small bounding boxes while allowing more flexibility for closer objects.

Overall, our adapted NLL loss for the symmetric output distribution is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{sym}}(C, \hat{C}, \Sigma) = \mathcal{R}(\Sigma, C) + (C - \hat{C})^\top \Sigma^{-1} (C - \hat{C}) = \mathcal{R}(\Sigma, C) + D_{\text{M,sym}}^2. \quad (3.29)$$

For the asymmetric variant, our loss function uses the asymmetrical Mahalanobis distance measure $D_{\text{M,asym}}$ defined in Equation 3.23. To regularize not only the size of the covariance Σ but also the skew parameter λ , we add an L_2 penalty on λ :

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{skew}}(\lambda) = \beta \|\lambda\|^2, \quad (3.30)$$

leading to the final loss function:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{asym}}(C, \hat{C}, \Sigma, \lambda) = \mathcal{R}(\Sigma, C) + D_{\text{M,asym}}^2 + \mathcal{R}_{\text{skew}}. \quad (3.31)$$

We compute the batch loss by taking the mean of the per-sample losses, either \mathcal{L}_{sym} or $\mathcal{L}_{\text{asym}}$, across all examples in the batch.

3.5.4 Implementation Details

We trained the PMF model under multiple parameter configurations for our experiments. In this work, we focus exclusively on object tracks labeled as *car*, producing anomaly scores s only for cars. However, the method can be used on any class, for instance, bicycles. As

mentioned in the previous sections, the PMF framework can easily be adapted to work on multiple classes.

Data Splits and Preprocessing

Consistent with all our AnDe approaches, we build a separate model for each camera scene. For each scene, the training dataset comprises preprocessed tracking data collected over a 24-hour period. In high-traffic scenarios, such as the roundabouts at Rangeline Medical Drive (Figure 3.2a) and Rangeline 116th Street (Figure 3.2b), this yields over one million car tracks. We also reserve an additional 50,000 single car tracks as a validation set to monitor performance on unseen data during training.

To investigate the effect of prediction horizon on anomaly detection, we explore three forecasting intervals $\delta \in \{0.5, 1, 2\}$ seconds. For each δ , we train two variants: one using symmetric probabilistic regression and one employing our asymmetric regression head.

During preprocessing (see Section 3.3.2), we discard any trajectory segments where the target vehicle appears in fewer than 80% of frames. To guarantee sufficient points for future-position interpolation at horizon δ , we apply a sliding window of length $1.1 \cdot \delta$ seconds.

Framework and Environment

Our PMF implementation is based on Python 3.10 and PyTorch 2.3.1. We load data in mini-batches of size 16. All experiments were run on an Ubuntu 24.04 server equipped with two NVIDIA GPUs: a GeForce RTX 4070 with 16 GB VRAM, and a GeForce RTX 3060 with 12 GB VRAM, using CUDA 12.4.

Backbone: MobileNet-V3

We selected MobileNet-V3 Small [HZC⁺17] as our backbone CNN due to its suitable trade-off between accuracy, parameter count, and fast inference. Its depthwise-separable convolutions reduce computational cost (FLOPs) and model size, and hence enable real-time inference on embedded platforms. Fast inference is especially important because we run AnDe models for different camera views in parallel on one server. MobileNet-V3 also introduces Squeeze-and-Excitation modules that adapt channel-wise feature scaling, which improves representational power for subtle traffic patterns.

To process our input, consisting of sine and cosine channels for target and context masks, we replaced MobileNet-V3’s first 3×3 convolution with a new layer accepting four input channels. We then removed the original classifier head and added our Gaussian-regression head.

Camera	symmetric			asymmetric		
	0.5 sec	1 sec	2 sec	0.5 sec	1 sec	2 sec
Ran Med	4.3×10^{-3} loss 0.017	1.4×10^{-3} loss 0.024	3.3×10^{-4} loss 0.047	2.1×10^{-3} loss 0.017	5.9×10^{-4} loss 0.024	2.0×10^{-4} loss 0.045
Ran 116th	2.9×10^{-3} loss 0.014	7.2×10^{-4} loss 0.022	2.7×10^{-4} loss 0.043	2.6×10^{-3} loss 0.014	4.1×10^{-4} loss 0.021	4.9×10^{-4} loss 0.043
Monon	1.2×10^{-4} loss 0.020	1.8×10^{-4} loss 0.036	1.3×10^{-4} loss 0.070	1.4×10^{-4} loss 0.020	1.2×10^{-4} loss 0.036	5.6×10^{-3} loss 0.067

Table 3.1: Results from the learning rate tuning on the Rangeline Medical Drive (Ran Med), Rangeline 116th St (Ran 116th) and Monon Elm St (Monon) cameras. The learning rate with the best loss for each model configuration (symmetric and asymmetric probabilistic regression with $\delta \in \{0.5, 1, 2\}$) is provided.

Training Loop, Optimizer, and Regularization

In our training loop, for each mini-batch we average the per-sample NLL loss (\mathcal{L}_{sym} or $\mathcal{L}_{\text{asym}}$), backpropagate, and step the optimizer. Every 10,000 batches, we evaluate on the validation set, record the training and validation losses, and apply early stopping after five consecutive non-improving checks to prevent overfitting. The model weights corresponding to the lowest loss are then used for inference and stored.

We use the Adam optimizer with a default learning rate of $\text{lr} = 1 \times 10^{-4}$, which is replaced if prior learning-rate hyperparameter tuning has been performed for the model’s parameter settings. PyTorch’s ReduceLRonPlateau scheduler monitors the validation loss. If the loss does not improve for two consecutive epochs, the learning rate is multiplied by 0.25. This reduction is applied at most twice over the course of training.

No additional regularization is applied to the MobileNet-V3 parameters. Instead, uncertainty estimates are regularized via our scaled trace penalty $\mathcal{R}(C, \Sigma)$ (see Section 3.5.3), and in the asymmetric case, L2-regularization of Equation 3.30 is applied to the skew parameters with $\beta = 0.01$.

Hyperparameter Tuning for Learning Rate

To determine the learning rate that yields the smallest final validation loss, we perform hyperparameter tuning by sampling ten initial learning rates over a log-uniform space $[1 \times 10^{-5}, 1 \times 10^{-2}]$. Each trial is trained until early stopping. After ten trials, the best-performing learning rate lr replaces the default 1×10^{-4} for that model configuration on that camera scene. The tuned learning rates are used to train our models for the experiments in Chapter 4.

Table 3.1 shows the results of the learning-rate tuning. The learning rate that yielded the lowest loss is reported for each model configuration. We observe that a smaller δ leads to a lower loss, which is reasonable, since predicting 0.5 s ahead is easier than 2 s. The symmetric and asymmetric models achieve very similar losses.

Reproducibility and Logging

In addition to the optimized model weights, all hyperparameters and final validation losses are stored in a JSON file. Full source code and environment specifications are available in our repository (github.com/starwit/movement-predictor) and the pretrained weights can be downloaded from [OneDrive](#).

4 Experiments

In this chapter, we evaluate the effectiveness of our Probabilistic Movement Forecaster (PMF) and the nearest-neighbor baseline (NNC). We develop an evaluation framework that makes anomaly labeling feasible by eliminating the need to manually review days of video footage. Section 4.1 describes the framework setup, and Section 4.2 details how we derive a novel, labeled anomaly dataset from it. In Section 4.3, we assess anomaly detection quality using normalized discounted cumulative gain (NDCG). Section 4.4 presents further studies, such as selecting an algorithm to aggregate per-detection anomaly scores into a single trajectory score.

4.1 Experimental Setup

To evaluate our anomaly detection models (AnDe models), we require ground-truth labels for anomalous trajectories. Manually inspecting days of video is infeasible, so we adopt a score-driven sampling strategy. The idea is to run all models and multiple model configurations on the same tracking data, use different scoring functions for ranking trajectories, and add the top-ranked trajectories for each model and scoring function in a common data pool. Only trajectories in this pool are manually labeled, making model evaluation feasible. By drawing anomaly candidates from different models and strategies, we ensure that almost all anomaly types are covered, reducing the risk of unlabeled events. Nevertheless, the resulting metrics are only approximate. While they can be reliably used for comparing different methods, we cannot guarantee that no anomalies are missed in our sampling and labeling process. An overview of the experimental setup is given in Figure 4.1. The procedure is described in detail in the following.

We train the PMF under six configurations. We pair three different prediction horizons $\delta \in \{0.5, 1, 2\}$ in seconds with symmetric and asymmetric regression heads. We denote symmetric models as SYM δ , for example SYM0.5 for $\delta = 0.5$, and asymmetric as ASYM δ . To account for randomness in initialization and optimization, we run five independent trials per configuration. Since our nearest neighbor baseline (NNC) is deterministic, it requires only one fit. In total, for each camera scene we thus train $6 \times 5 = 30$ PMF models plus a single NNC, provided on [OneDrive](#).

The experiments are performed on three camera views: the Rangeline Medical Drive (Figure 3.2a), Rangeline 116th Street (Figure 3.2b) and Monon Elm Street (Figure 3.2d). The Rangeline scenes are more likely to capture traffic-safety-critical behavior, as they depict major roads converging and thus experience heavy traffic. By contrast, Monon Elm Street is an intersection in a pedestrian area where vehicles usually drive slowly, with fewer cars and more pedestrians and bicycles. We include this camera to evaluate our models across markedly different scenes. The training dataset for each camera covers 24 hours video footage, and the test dataset that is used for model evaluation consists of tracks from a

Figure 4.1: Overview of the experimental setup: inference of anomaly scores, trajectory ranking by multiple score metrics, selection of top candidates, manual labeling, creation of the anomaly test set and finally evaluating model and ranking functions performances based on the anomaly labels. The model training process and the training dataset are omitted for simplicity.

time interval of 48 hours. Using a longer time period becomes impractical because we must store not only detection and tracking data but also the video frames needed to later visualize detected anomalies. We decided to rather use only 48 hours of footage across three different camera views instead of a full week for a single camera. We restrict our experiments to cars. The used video frame rate is 10, so for each car, we get at most 10 anomaly scores per second.

In the data selection process for labeling, we use multiple trajectory-ranking methods to capture both short-lived spikes and sustained anomalies over time. For each trajectory T_j , we sort its N_j per-detection scores in descending order $s_{(1),j} \geq s_{(2),j} \geq \dots \geq s_{(N_j),j}$. We then define ranking functions based on this order:

$$\text{score}^{(k)}(j) = s_{(k),j}, \quad k \in \{1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50\}. \quad (4.1)$$

Given these six trajectory scores for each car j we rank all trajectories in the 48h-video footage. From each ranking, we collect the highest top 50 trajectories for later labeling. Using $\text{score}^{(1)}$ highlights trajectories with a single large anomaly peak, while $\text{score}^{(10)}$, $\text{score}^{(20)}$, and $\text{score}^{(50)}$ emphasize trajectories whose 10th, 20th, or 50th highest scores remain high, thus ensuring we capture both extreme anomalies and behaviors that are consistently anomalous.

After collecting all anomaly candidates, short videos are stored in which the car whose trajectory has been detected as anomalous is marked. These videos allow full inspection of each situation, and we manually decide whether they depict anomalous behavior. Moreover, we distinguish different categories of anomalous behavior, for instance, driving too fast or driving against traffic. In total, we distinguish 32 different anomalous events, which are described in detail in the next section. Further, each event category is assigned one of five degrees of relevancy. Some anomalies are more important to the user because they involve dangerous behavior and are therefore given a higher relevance degree. In our experiments, models whose predicted anomalies predominantly capture dangerous situations are preferred over models whose anomalies, while unusual, are less critical for traffic safety.

The main evaluation metric in our experiments is NDCG, since it naturally incorporates degrees of relevancy and shows which model configurations and trajectory scoring functions achieve the best overall performance. In further studies, we additionally examine AU-PR for selected categories to gain insights into model performance on specific dangerous events.

4.2 Dataset Creation and Annotation

We have created a novel anomaly dataset comprising 32 different types of anomalous traffic situations with more than 1000 found anomalies. Our *Overhead Traffic Anomalies (OTA)* dataset is available on Hugging Face huggingface.co/datasets/starwit/overhead-traffic-anomalies for future research.

4.2.1 Annotated Events

This section defines the event categories that are used to label each anomaly candidate. Each candidate trajectory, identified by one or more scoring strategies, is exported as a short video clip in which the tracked vehicle is highlighted. We then review each clip and assign one of the labels described in Table 4.1 .

Each labeled candidate is recorded as a JSON object with three fields: *obj_id*, a unique vehicle identifier; *label*, an integer drawn from $\{-1, 0, 1, \dots, 32\}$ and *time_interval*, a two-element array of UNIX timestamps $[t_{\text{start}}, t_{\text{end}}]$ that mark the period of the detected anomalous behavior.

Defining 32 distinct anomaly categories, and reserving “0” for normal behavior and “-1” for errors in the input data, offers several advantages. Explicitly marking detection and tracking mistakes is important, since some error types cannot be fully removed during preprocessing and should not influence the evaluation of our models. For example, the roof of a truck may occasionally be misclassified as a car. That erroneous bounding box then appears in an implausible location for a car and falsely triggers anomaly detection. By tagging such cases as -1, we ensure these artifacts do not influence our performance metrics.

Describing each detected situation in fine detail is crucial for assigning appropriate relevance levels. Small variations in a traffic incident can strongly change its severity.

Label	Description
-1	The anomaly score was triggered by a spurious bounding-box or ID switch rather than by true vehicle behavior.
0	False positive (FP): The vehicle's motion is entirely normal, no anomaly occurred.
1	Lane change.
2	Late turn: nearly missing the curve by entering too far or too fast.
3	Cutting inside turns, such as crossing the centerline for a "shorter" path.
4	Driving on the centerline between lanes moving in the same direction.
5	Waiting or moving aside to let emergency vehicles pass.
6	Short wait at an empty intersection.
7	Long wait (several seconds) at an empty intersection.
8	Stopping too far into the main road while waiting at an intersection.
9	Random stop/wait at an unusual location, for instance on an empty roundabout or intersection.
10	Random slowdown at an unusual location (empty roundabout or intersection).
11	Fast driving (recklessly).
12	Very slow driving, driver seems insecure.
13	Any kind of "weird" movement, such as driving very slow with stops or driving in zigzags.
14	Brief reverse movement, for example adjusting position at an intersection.
15	Approaching slow or stopped vehicles at uncommon points (e.g. high traffic).
16	Traffic tie-up.
17	Nearly cutting off another traffic agent (should have yielded).
18	Clearly cutting off another traffic agent (driving very fast and/or forcing the other agent to brake).
19	Near-collision.
20	Needlessly driving into the oncoming lane (not for overtaking)
21	Illegal turn (such as turning left at an intersection where only going straight or right is allowed).
22	Short wrong-way driving in roundabout (but vehicle exits correctly).
23	Wrong-way driving on a public road.
24	Driving more than one full round in a roundabout.
25	Broken-down vehicle on a public road.
26	Stopping mid-street to let a pedestrian cross.
27	Stopping at a designated pedestrian crossing.
28	Drifting slightly off the road while driving.
29	Vehicle getting on or parking on the sidewalk.
30	Sudden, heavy braking.
31	Swerve to avoid another vehicle or maneuver around a vehicle.
32	Other risky behavior that does not fit to another category or is an extreme variant of one or more event categories.

Table 4.1: Descriptions of all defined anomaly labels.

Degree	Description	Assigned Event Categories
0	FP and uninteresting events	0, 1
1	Rather uninteresting anomaly	3, 4, 6, 8, 15, 17, 27
2	Relevant anomaly	2, 5, 7, 10, 12, 16, 24, 26, 30, 31
3	High relevance	9, 11, 14, 18, 20, 21, 28, 29
4	Critical relevance: dangerous behavior	13, 19, 22, 23, 25, 32

Table 4.2: Relevance Degrees for Anomaly Events

For example, cutting off another vehicle is always noteworthy, but its danger depends on context: it might be a momentary driver error, or it could involve a car speeding through an intersection without regard for oncoming traffic. The latter is an event dangerous enough that the police might be alerted. This variability motivates the use of many granular event categories. Deciding on a category is also subjective, for instance, determining when a cut-off was so close that a collision could only be prevented at the last moment (category 19).

Table 4.2 shows the mapping of event categories to five degrees of relevance. The assignment is subjective and might differ depending on which anomalous scenarios the user is most interested in. The chosen mapping reflects a user’s need to act quickly when crashes, reckless drivers, or potentially impaired and disoriented drivers are observed, while also gathering statistics on all traffic-rule violations. The structured annotation paired with relevance degrees supports both broad-scale model comparison and fine-grained analyses of individual anomaly categories.

4.2.2 Dataset Composition

Our anomaly dataset is organized by camera, with each camera folder including a train and a test set. Only the test set contains anomaly annotations. A global `event_labels.txt` file defines the meaning of each anomaly category ID, very similar to Table 4.1, and a `relevance_mapping.json` specifies the mapping from category IDs to the relevance degrees used in our experiments and shown in Table 4.2.

Training Set

The training set consists of the preprocessed traffic-agent trajectories that we use to train our models. In detail, it contains all smoothed agent detections¹, and all video frames within a 24-hour period. A detection consists of the bounding box b , the YOLOv8 object class label c with its confidence score, the timestamp t of the frame in which it was detected, and the identifier j that assigns each detection to its trajectory T_j . We additionally provide geo-location information, which are the detection’s longitude and latitude calculated from the Starwit Awareness Engine’s geo mapper. Although our current AnDe models do not use this geo information, it is valuable for future work and research.

¹preprocessing without the last *track selection* step, see Figure 3.3

```

[
  {
    "timestamp": 1753859640873,
    "frame_index": 100,
    "frame_key": "frame_1753859640873_000100.jpg",
    "shard": "frames-000000.tar",
    "detections": [
      {
        "class_id": 2,
        "object_id": "29f3a4197afa32f7bef51257d0ad1b4c",
        "longitude": -86.12962,
        "latitude": 39.97545,
        "boundingbox": [0.226, 0.074, 0.2757, 0.1333],
        "confidence": 0.646
      },
      ...
    ]
  },
  ...
]

```

Figure 4.2: Minimal extract from the anomaly datasets agent detections of the Monon Elm Street camera scene.

The video frames, downsampled to 320×180 , are provided as WebDataset .tar shards, for example "frames-000123.tar", with about 10,000 JPEG frames per shard. Inside each shard, files are named with the capture timestamp in milliseconds plus a simple running index, for instance "frame_1750682213626_000042.jpg". A companion "index.csv" lists each frame's filename, timestamp, and shard so users can easily align frames with annotations.

The agent detections are provided in a JSON file "object_detections.json". Each entry contains the fields *timestamp*, *frame_index*, *frame_key*, *shard*, and *detections*. The field *timestamp* is the UNIX epoch time in milliseconds. *frame_index* is the sequential index of the frame image, *frame_key* its filename, and *shard* identifies which tar shard contains the image. *detections* lists all detections recorded for that timestamp. Each detection record includes the *class_id*, for instance 2 for "car", the *object_id* as a unique hex string, *longitude* and *latitude* GPS coordinates if available, the *boundingbox* represented as $[x_{\min}, y_{\min}, x_{\max}, y_{\max}]$ normalized to image size, and *confidence*. A minimal example is shown in Figure 4.2.

Test Set with Anomaly Annotations

The test set shares the training set's structure but includes an extra file, "anomaly-labels.csv," containing the anomaly annotations. Hence, for each camera scene, the test data set consists of a directory containing the frames "frames_shards" with their "index.csv", the detections file "object_detections.json", and the anomaly labels "anomaly-labels.csv". The "anomaly-labels.csv" summarizes the found anomalous events in the test dataset in Table 4.3. The CSV specifies the vehicle causing the anomaly by its *object_id*, the time interval during which it occurs and the anomaly label. We include only true anomalies (labels 1 to 32) and tracking errors (label -1). Trajectories flagged as false positives (label 0) are not listed, because unlabeled trajectories are implicitly considered normal.

object_id	start_timestamp	end_timestamp	label
b0cba77...28e8636	1753936536900	1753936539305	31
933b01e...86a94a1	1753926439175	1753926444685	12
7b2b0d6...4f93ef6	1753890943280	1753890950093	10
59bb680...56abb2c	1753746001379	1753746002980	20
2f6bce3...c2588e5	1729699903126	1729699904629	9
...

Table 4.3: Example labels.csv.

We encourage researchers to examine the unlabeled trajectories, as they may reveal additional anomalies that our models missed. Newly found candidates can be labeled and contributed to the dataset. Because we release both the training split and all anomaly candidates identified by our AnDe models, the results of our experiments serve as a clear, reproducible comparison baseline for future research. We also plan to expand the dataset with more highly relevant anomalies by adding short video clips of anomalous behavior observed during deployment at Starwit.

Distribution of Anomalous Events

Figure 4.3 shows the distribution of anomalous events in our test sets for each camera scene. On Monon Elm Street, we detected 309 anomalous events, on Rangeline Medical Drive 344, and 374 on Rangeline 116th Street. In the histograms, anomaly categories are ordered by relevance, with the least relevant on the right and the most relevant on the left. The relative order of categories within the same relevance degree on the x-axis is arbitrary. The most dangerous categories occur less frequently than others. Still, we detected eight instances of drivers driving in the wrong direction (categories 22 and 23) and eight near collisions, which is surprisingly high.

Across the three scenes, there are some huge differences regarding the frequencies of several anomaly types. At the large roundabout of the Rangeline 116th Street Scene, we observed many illegal turns (category 21) as drivers repeatedly turn left to stay on the outer lane, which only allows straight travel to exit at the next junction. This behavior could easily lead to collisions with vehicles in the inner lane. On Rangeline Medical Drive, however, drivers on the roundabout tend to be overly cautious or insecure about their right of way, often slowing down when other vehicles approach the scene (categories 10 and 12). Here we also detected many cars caught in a traffic-tie up (category 16). On Monon Elm Street, we observe many drivers briefly entering the opposite, oncoming lane when preparing to turn left (category 20), as well as several cars driving or stopping off the road on the sidewalk (category 29). Since vehicle traffic in this scene is usually light, we observed far fewer situations in which cars cut off other traffic agents or failed to yield (category 18). These different frequencies of relevant anomaly types make it interesting to analyze how anomaly detection models perform across the different scenes.

Unlike most public benchmarks, which typically target static object detection like DOTA [YWX⁺23a] or provide only short clips of each scene, our dataset is designed specifically for fine-grained traffic anomalies in realistic urban scenes. We offer 32 narrowly defined event

Figure 4.3: Distribution of detected anomaly types over 48 hours for each camera. The most relevant types are on the left and the less relevant ones on the right of the x-axis.

categories with different relevance degrees rather than aggregating all unusual motions into a single anomaly class. Each of three camera views contributes 24 hours of train data, complete with per-frame JSON detections and downsampled video frames. We also label tracking errors (-1) to prevent spurious detections from skewing results. This combination of scale, granularity, and full visual context makes our dataset a robust baseline for future anomaly-detection research.

4.3 Results and Comparison to Baseline

In this section, we present the experimental outcomes of our framework. We compare the performance of the PMF implementations with nearest-neighbor-based motion clustering (NNC). In Section 4.3.1, we visualize the detected anomaly candidates from both approaches, to illustrate why these candidates received high anomaly scores. Section 4.3.2 provides an overview of the distribution of detected anomaly labels in the top 50 candidates, followed by Section 4.3.3, which analyzes the NDCG results, including both the general anomaly types found in the top 50 and their ranking order.

Figure 4.4: Top 50 anomaly candidates detected by our nearest neighbor-based motion clustering (NNC) with ranking functions score⁽⁵⁾ and score⁽¹⁰⁾. Detections with an anomaly score above the respective threshold are marked by a small black arrow pointing in the car’s direction of motion θ . Some relevant anomaly labels are highlighted: red trajectories indicate wrong-way driving (22, 23), orange indicates illegal turns (21), yellow indicates a car driving or parking on the sidewalk (29), and cyan indicates driving slightly off the road (28).

4.3.1 Visualization of Top-50 Anomalies

The NNC method, described in Section 3.4.2, groups similar motion directions at predefined grid points over the camera scene. Motions that do not fit into any cluster receive a high anomaly score, while motions detected at grid points without cluster information receive an even higher score.

Figure 4.4 shows the top 50 anomaly candidates detected by NNC and ranked by score⁽¹⁰⁾ (Figures 4.4a and 4.4b) and score⁽⁵⁾ (Figure 4.4c). Individual high-scoring detections are shown as black arrows indicating the direction of movement. The arrows belong to the trajectories ranked in the top 50. For each trajectory in the top 50 of score⁽¹⁰⁾, we display only detections whose anomaly score s exceeds the threshold $\tau = \min \text{score}^{(10)}$, meaning the individual score s is larger than the score⁽¹⁰⁾ of the trajectory ranked 50th. The same procedure is applied for score⁽⁵⁾ in Figure 4.4c. This highlights the most anomalous segments of each trajectory. Selected relevant anomaly types are colored in the visualizations. Overall, this approach makes anomalies detected by the NNC method easily interpretable.

Anomalies detected by the PMF models are shown in Figure 4.5. Here, individual high-scoring detections are visualized directly on the scene’s frame image, making the scores more interpretable. Seven anomaly candidates from different camera scenes are shown, each with five detections. A per-detection anomaly score is the Mahalanobis distance between the predicted expected future position (red dot) and the actual observed future position (red cross), with the cyan contour representing equal Mahalanobis distance from the predicted center. The visibly large red dot–red cross separations relative to the cyan contour correspond to high per-detection scores, which lead to high trajectory rankings.

(a) Illegal u-turn - category 21 (Monon Elm Street, PMF ASYM2).

(b) Wrong-way-driver (backwards driving) & turning - category 22 (Monon Elm Street, PMF ASYM2).

(c) Car driving on the sidewalk - category 29 (Monon Elm Street, PMF ASYM2).

(d) Weird, insecure driving: very slow with stops - category 13 (Rangeline Medical Drive, PMF ASYM2).

(e) Wrong-way-driver in roundabout - category 22 (Rangeline Medical Drive, PMF ASYM2).

(f) Fast driving - category 11 (Rangeline 116th Street, PMF SYM0.5).

(g) Failing to yield and stopping on the roundabout - category 18 (Rangeline 116th Street, PMF SYM0.5).

Figure 4.5: Visualization of detected anomalies by PMF models ($\text{SYM}\delta$, $\text{ASYM}\delta$). The *red dot* indicates the predicted expected future position \hat{C} , δ seconds ahead. The *red cross*, highlighted by the arrow, marks the actual observed future position C . Points along the *cyan contour* have the same Mahalanobis distance from the predicted center \hat{C} . This contour visualizes the predicted motion variance. Bounding boxes for surrounding traffic agents are omitted for clarity.

This visualization also reveals how the model captures anomalies. For example, for wrong-way drivers (Figures 4.5b and 4.5e), the predicted probability distribution peaks on the opposite side of the actual observed position. The probabilistic CNN also models high prediction uncertainty, visible in the second and third images of Figure 4.5a, where the car’s orientation is ambiguous due to the unusual nature of the illegal turn. This results in a higher predicted variance, shown by a larger cyan contour, which motivates including the variance size in the calculation of anomaly scores. However, higher variances are also observed for vehicles in the foreground and in areas where multiple turning options exist, such as intersections, which is why variance size was excluded from the anomaly score in this work, leaving this for future research.

In comparison, the visualizations show that the PMF model can capture a broader variety of anomalies, while the NNC method mainly detects position- and direction-based anomalies. The NNC method cannot detect behaviors like slow, insecure driving (Figure 4.5d), speeding (Figure 4.5f), or context-dependent anomalies such as failing to yield (Figure 4.5g).

4.3.2 Distribution of Anomaly Labels across Models and Rankings

To compare the top-50 anomaly label distributions between the PMF models and the NNC, we present histograms showing the frequencies of each of the 32 anomaly labels, as well as false positives (category 0) and detection or tracking errors (category -1). Figure 4.6 shows the results for each camera scene. The anomaly categories are ordered by relevance, with the most relevant on the left and the least relevant on the right.

Presenting all combinations of six PMF model configurations and six trajectory rankings would make a first comparison overly complex. Therefore, Figure 4.6 includes only one representative PMF model per camera and three trajectory rankings: the two extremes, score⁽¹⁾ and score⁽⁵⁰⁾, and the intermediate score⁽¹⁰⁾. Hence, for each camera, three histograms are shown for a PMF model and three for the NNC approach. Because five models were trained for each PMF configuration, the PMF histograms (upper rows) display the average label frequencies. The black box-plot-like intervals at the top of each bar represent the standard deviation across the five models. The complete set of histograms for all model-ranking combinations is provided in the appendix.

Comparison with the Nearest Neighbor Approach

The NNC method generally produces more false positives and low-relevance anomalies compared to PMF models, shown by the tall bars at the right of the histograms. In general, the PMF models tend to detect more useful anomalies. An exception is Monon Elm Street, where both methods yield similar frequencies for low-relevance events (relevance degrees 0 and 1).

The NNC approach performs poorly on anomaly types it was not designed to detect, such as speed-related or interaction-based anomalies, including fast driving (11), cutting off other vehicles (18), slow driving (12), and traffic tie-ups (16). However, it captures certain position- and direction-based anomalies better, such as illegal turns (21) at Rangeline

(a) Rangeline Medical Drive

(b) Rangeline 116th Street

(c) Monon Elm Street

Figure 4.6: Histograms showing the frequencies of detected anomaly labels among the top 50 candidates for a selected PMF model configuration and the NNC. Results are shown separately for each of the three camera scenes and for three ranking functions $\text{score}^{(1)}$, $\text{score}^{(10)}$ and $\text{score}^{(50)}$ to illustrate the range from extreme to more sustained anomalies.

116th Street and vehicles driving onto the sidewalk (29) at Monon Elm Street. For off-road detections, where no cluster data exists, the method assigns very high anomaly scores, as described in Section 3.4.2, so the method very precisely detects off-road anomalies as illustrated in Figure 4.4.

Effect of Trajectory Ranking Functions on PMF Results

Trajectory ranking functions that account for a longer sequence of high per-detection anomaly scores like $\text{score}^{(50)}$, tend to include fewer false positives (category 0) and fewer detection/tracking errors (category -1), as shown by the shorter purple and gray bars. Anomalies that persist over time, such as slow driving (12) and traffic tie-ups (16), are more frequent in rankings $\text{score}^{(k)}$ with higher k , while short-lived anomalies, such as brief lane intrusions (20) at Monon Elm Street or fast driving (11) at Rangeline 116th Street, are more prominent in rankings with lower k . This shows that top anomaly candidates can vary substantially across trajectory ranking functions, making it worthwhile to analyze multiple ranking functions for each model.

These visual observations provide an initial intuition and high-level overview of the models' performances. However, a thorough evaluation requires performance metrics such as the NDCG, which account for relevance degrees and can reveal more nuanced performance differences, for instance, between PMF configurations. Still, the histograms in this section remain valuable, as they highlight differences in individual anomaly labels rather than only aggregated relevance scores.

4.3.3 Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain

To quantitatively evaluate the ranking quality of detected anomalies, we compute the Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (NDCG), described in Section 2.1.4, for each model configuration and ranking function $\text{score}^{(k)}$. The NDCG is calculated using the relevance degrees defined in Table 4.2. For each model, we first rank all anomaly trajectories in the labeled data pool based on the chosen $\text{score}^{(k)}$, exclude all tracking and detection errors labeled as category -1 , and then select the top 50, thus computing NDCG@50. Candidates labeled as -1 are excluded because they arise from input data errors rather than genuine anomalous behavior and should not influence the performance results of our models. In the following, we refer to NDCG@50 simply as NDCG.

The results are presented in Table 4.4. We have five models for each PMF configuration and report the mean NDCG across these runs, with the standard deviation between models given in smaller font size. For the nearest neighbor-based motion clustering (NNC) we report the results of the single model.

Across cameras, the best-performing models are ASYM2 for Rangeline Medical Drive and Monon Elm Street, and SYM0.5 / ASYM0.5 for Rangeline 116th Street. Compared to the NNC model, results confirm the observations from Section 4.3.2: on both Rangeline cameras, PMF models consistently outperform NNC for all ranking functions. On Monon Elm Street, however, NNC achieves best performance for $\text{score}^{(20)}$ and $\text{score}^{(50)}$, but its best NDCG of 0.76 is still below the top PMF performance, as ASYM2 achieves 0.82 for the trajectory ranking $\text{score}^{(5)}$.

Method	score ⁽¹⁾	score ⁽²⁾	score ⁽⁵⁾	score ⁽¹⁰⁾	score ⁽²⁰⁾	score ⁽⁵⁰⁾
Rangeline Medical Drive						
SYM0.5	0.52 ±0.02	0.59 ±0.02	0.60 ±0.03	0.59 ±0.03	0.57 ±0.05	0.56 ±0.01
ASYM0.5	0.53 ±0.03	0.60 ±0.03	0.61 ±0.03	0.61 ±0.02	0.57 ±0.02	0.56 ±0.02
SYM1	0.44 ±0.04	0.53 ±0.02	0.59 ±0.05	0.64 ±0.03	0.64 ±0.03	0.60 ±0.01
ASYM1	0.47 ±0.06	0.58 ±0.06	0.65 ±0.03	0.65 ±0.04	0.64 ±0.04	0.61 ±0.01
SYM2	0.40 ±0.05	0.41 ±0.05	0.51 ±0.07	0.62 ±0.03	0.63 ±0.04	0.63 ±0.01
ASYM2	0.51 ±0.07	0.54 ±0.06	0.67 ±0.03	0.74 ±0.02	0.73 ±0.02	0.63 ±0.01
NNC	0.38	0.45	0.53	0.48	0.43	0.37
Rangeline 116th Street						
SYM0.5	0.48 ±0.02	0.52 ±0.01	0.54 ±0.01	0.54 ±0.01	0.53 ±0.01	0.51 ±0.01
ASYM0.5	0.47 ±0.03	0.52 ±0.01	0.53 ±0.01	0.53 ±0.01	0.52 ±0.01	0.51 ±0.01
SYM1	0.34 ±0.02	0.38 ±0.01	0.42 ±0.02	0.45 ±0.02	0.47 ±0.01	0.48 ±0.01
ASYM1	0.35 ±0.03	0.43 ±0.02	0.50 ±0.01	0.49 ±0.01	0.48 ±0.01	0.49 ±0.01
SYM2	0.28 ±0.03	0.31 ±0.03	0.45 ±0.03	0.50 ±0.01	0.50 ±0.00	0.47 ±0.01
ASYM2	0.27 ±0.02	0.33 ±0.01	0.46 ±0.01	0.47 ±0.01	0.50 ±0.01	0.48 ±0.01
NNC	0.29	0.29	0.38	0.36	0.41	0.34
Monon Elm Street						
SYM0.5	0.72 ±0.03	0.73 ±0.04	0.76 ±0.04	0.76 ±0.01	0.69 ±0.01	0.65 ±0.02
ASYM0.5	0.70 ±0.05	0.73 ±0.05	0.77 ±0.04	0.78 ±0.02	0.70 ±0.03	0.68 ±0.02
SYM1	0.75 ±0.03	0.77 ±0.04	0.76 ±0.02	0.78 ±0.02	0.67 ±0.03	0.63 ±0.03
ASYM1	0.67 ±0.02	0.70 ±0.03	0.77 ±0.03	0.77 ±0.02	0.67 ±0.01	0.63 ±0.02
SYM2	0.69 ±0.08	0.73 ±0.06	0.76 ±0.04	0.74 ±0.03	0.66 ±0.04	0.62 ±0.03
ASYM2	0.75 ±0.02	0.79 ±0.02	0.82 ±0.01	0.77 ±0.03	0.65 ±0.03	0.63 ±0.07
NNC	0.74	0.75	0.76	0.75	0.75	0.72

Table 4.4: NDCG results for each model and each scoring function score^(k). For the PMF model configuration is the average NDCG result of the five trained models given and the standard deviation between is provided in smaller fontsize. The three best results as well as the best performing model are highlighted for each camera.

The standard deviations of PMF models with the same configuration are mostly small (0.01–0.03), particularly for the best performance results. This indicates that the corresponding configurations can be considered significantly better than the other examined configurations for our data pool.

When evaluating symmetric versus asymmetric variants at the same prediction horizon $\delta \in \{0.5, 1, 2\}$, we find that on Rangeline Medical Drive, ASYM consistently outperforms SYM. On Rangeline 116th Street, no clear trend is visible, though SYM0.5 slightly outperforms ASYM0.5, while ASYM1 slightly outperforms SYM1. On Monon Elm Street, differences are also small, except for $\delta = 2$, where ASYM2 shows a clear advantage over SYM2. Overall, the asymmetric output performed better.

Regarding the influence of the ranking functions, mid-range k values, particularly score⁽⁵⁾, score⁽¹⁰⁾, and score⁽²⁰⁾, tend to produce the highest NDCG scores across all models. This

is reasonable, as the histograms from the previous section show that $\text{score}^{(1)}$, which considers only the single highest per-detection anomaly score in a trajectory, tends to capture more false positives. Conversely, $\text{score}^{(50)}$, which is based solely on the 50th-highest per-detection score, fails to capture short-term anomalies, such as brief instances of speeding. These results highlight that the choice of ranking function substantially impacts performance, often more than model architecture or prediction horizon. Given this strong influence, it is worth exploring more advanced trajectory ranking functions that aggregate anomaly evidence over larger portions of the trajectory rather than relying solely on a single k -th best per-detection score.

4.4 Further Studies

The results presented so far have established that our PMF models outperform the NNC baseline and provide meaningful trajectory-level anomaly rankings. However, several open questions remain. In particular, the choice of the trajectory ranking function, the evaluation of model performance across different anomaly relevance degrees, and the robustness against erroneous detections or tracks can substantially affect the practical utility of the anomaly detection system.

This section therefore complements the main evaluation by conducting a series of additional studies. First, we investigate advanced trajectory ranking functions that go beyond the initial $\text{score}^{(k)}$ formulation in Section 4.4.1. Next in Section 4.4.2, we analyze the models under different severity levels of anomalies using the AU-PR performance metric. Finally, we test the robustness of the models in the presence of mistakes in the input detections and tracks, which are unavoidable in real-world deployments. Together, these studies aim to identify a generalizable PMF configuration and scoring function while also assessing the resilience of the system to realistic sources of error.

4.4.1 Advanced Trajectory Ranking Functions

In this section, we evaluate further trajectory-level aggregation functions that combine per-detection anomaly scores into a single trajectory score. After a final analysis on $\text{score}^{(k)}$ for various k we focus on two main categories: top- k -based aggregation and percentile-based aggregation, both common in related anomaly-detection pipelines that select single detections or detections above a quantile before scoring trajectories [DMdS⁺20, VTE⁺19]. Based on these results, we aim to identify a PMF model configuration and a single aggregation function that generalizes well across all three camera locations.

For each trajectory T_j , we sort the per-detection anomaly scores in descending order, $s_{(1),j} \geq \dots \geq s_{(N_j),j}$, with N_j detections per trajectory. These per-detection scores s are produced by our models for each trajectory in the labeled data pool, excluding those labeled as input mistakes (category -1). We exclude such YOLOv8 mistakes because Starwit is continuously fine-tuning the detection and tracking modules, and the frequency of these errors is expected to decrease rapidly. As in the previous section, we evaluate each ranking function by analyzing only the top 50 anomaly candidates using NDCG@50, hereafter referred to simply as NDCG, to ensure comparability.

Figure 4.7: NDCG results for the $\text{score}^{(k)}$ ranking function across different k . Each curve, except NNC, shows the mean over five PMF models per configuration, with shaded regions indicating ± 0.5 standard deviations.

Since evaluating new aggregation functions on the full 48-hour test set would be computationally expensive, we restrict ranking to the labeled data pool. While this may not yield the exact same top-50 as the full dataset, the pool already covers nearly all relevant anomalies as explained in Section 4.1. Thus, the approximation remains reliable and ensures consistent comparisons across functions. In total, we rank 615 trajectories from Rangeline Medical Drive, 600 from Rangeline 116th Street, and 389 from Monon Elm Street.

Ranking Function $\text{score}^{(k)}$ for Various k

Recall our initial ranking function $\text{score}^{(k)}(j) = s_{(k),j}$ from Formula 4.1 that uses the k -th best detection $s_{(k),j}$. Figure 4.7 shows NDCG values across different k to visually analyze how the NDCG changes with k . In the plots, the standard deviations among the five PMF models per configuration are indicated by shaded regions. The six initial scoring functions are highlighted by crosses. The vertical grid lines correspond to an NDCG difference of 0.05, which simplifies visual comparison across models and cameras.

Overall, the NDCG curves develop smoothly, with stable standard deviations across k , although the NNC, shown in a black dotted line, tends to exhibit more fluctuations. Most models peak below $k = 20$, while very small k , especially $k < 5$, often lead to poor results. On Monon Elm Street, NDCG drops sharply for $k > 10$, whereas on the Rangeline cameras performance remains more stable. These findings are consistent with the observations from the previous section.

The sharp drop in NDCG on Monon Elm Street can be explained by the types of anomalies typically observed at that scene. Many relevant anomalies here contain few very strong signals, for example illegal turns (category 21), vehicles leaving the road (categories 28 and 29), or short periods of driving on the opposite lane (category 20). These cases often produce single per-detection scores with extremely high Mahalanobis distances, since the predicted future positions frequently lie far from the actual observed positions, as illustrated in several frames in Figures 4.5a–4.5c. In such situations, using a small k to include only the highest scores ensures that these anomalies are ranked highly. By contrast, using a larger k is more meaningful for anomalies, which are characterized by slightly elevated anomaly scores across longer periods, such as suspiciously slow or insecure

driving (categories 12 and 13). Since slow driving and frequent stops are common at Monon Elm Street, as a scene with many pedestrians, using a larger k in this setting produces less useful trajectory anomaly scores.

Top- k Based Aggregation

Top- k aggregation combines the k highest per-detection anomaly scores within a trajectory into a single trajectory score. In contrast to the $\text{score}^{(k)}$ function, which uses only the k -th best score, these aggregation functions integrate information from a larger portion of the trajectory. We also consider values of k larger than 50, because $k = 50$ corresponds to a time span of only five seconds.² For large k , it may occur that k exceeds the length of a trajectory. In such cases, the top- k aggregation for trajectory T_j reduces to the top- N_j aggregation, where N_j denotes the number of detections in trajectory T_j .

We define three top- k aggregation functions for scoring a trajectory T_j :

$$\text{Top-}k \text{ average: } \text{score}_{\text{avg}}^{(k)}(j) = \frac{1}{\min(k, N_j)} \sum_{i=1}^{\min(k, N_j)} s_{(i),j}, \quad (4.2)$$

$$\text{Top-}k \text{ median: } \text{score}_{\text{med}}^{(k)}(j) = \text{median}\{s_{(1),j}, s_{(2),j}, \dots, s_{(\min(k, N_j)),j}\}, \quad (4.3)$$

$$\text{Top-}k \text{ lin. weighted average: } \text{score}_{\text{wavg}}^{(k)}(j) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{\min(k, N_j)} (\min(k, N_j) - i + 1) s_{(i),j}}{\sum_{i=1}^{\min(k, N_j)} (\min(k, N_j) - i + 1)}, \quad (4.4)$$

where $\min(k, N_j)$ is the minimum of k and N_j . While the top- k averaging score $\text{score}_{\text{avg}}^{(k)}$ assigns equal weight to all top- k scores, the linearly weighted average score $\text{score}_{\text{wavg}}^{(k)}$ assigns decreasing linear weights from the highest to the k -th score and thus emphasizes the highest scores of a trajectory.

Several existing approaches similarly aggregate per-detection or per-segment scores into trajectory-level anomaly scores. For instance, Dias et al. [DMdS⁺20] use likelihoods computed with normalizing flows to detect trajectory-level anomalies. They combine the likelihoods across segments into a single trajectory score using median or average aggregation functions.

We exclude the NNC baseline from this experiment because its per-detection anomaly scores s are not on a consistent scale. Scores outside clustered regions, such as the yellow segment in Figure 4.4c, are computed differently and are typically much larger than the z-score-based values within clusters. Although these scores can still be ranked to obtain the top- k detections, aggregating them into a trajectory score, for example by averaging, is not meaningful, as the few extremely large values outside clustered regions would dominate the result.

²Note the distinction between the two notations: top- k aggregation refers to using the k highest per-detection scores *within a single trajectory* to compute its trajectory score, while the “top 50” used for the NDCG calculation (NDCG@50) refers to the 50 highest-ranked *trajectories across the labeled dataset* after all anomaly candidates have been ordered by their trajectory scores.

Figure 4.8: NDCG curves for top- k aggregation functions (average, median, and linearly weighted average) across three camera scenes. Shaded regions indicate ± 0.5 standard deviations.

Figure 4.8 shows the NDCG results for our PMF models. Beyond $k = 200$ the curves stagnate, so we restrict the plots to $k \in [1, 250]$. Compared to the simple $\text{score}^{(k)}$ -based ranking, the aggregated functions generally reach higher peaks. The methods that performed best for each camera in the previous analysis remain the strongest here as well, for example ASYM2 for Rangeline Medical Drive and Monon Elm Street. Here, ASYM2 achieves an NDCG of 0.8 on Rangeline Medical Drive, whereas the same model only achieved around 0.75 with $\text{score}^{(k)}$ ranking. SYM0.5 on Rangeline 116th Street increases from 0.55 to 0.6. On Monon Elm Street, however, the best model (ASYM2) remains at 0.82 without further improvement.

Across all cameras, there are no substantial differences between median, average, and weighted average aggregation. However, the effect of k again varies strongly across cameras. On Rangeline 116th Street, larger values of k lead to higher NDCG values, with SYM0.5 peaking near the full trajectory. On Rangeline Medical Drive, models peak

around $k \in [40, 100]$, corresponding to roughly four to ten seconds of trajectory data. On Monon Elm Street, the best performance is again achieved for very low k , around $k = 10$, corresponding to about one second of trajectory data.

These results highlight the strong influence of the interval size k . Since trajectory lengths differ across scenes, it is impractical to define a single fixed k that generalizes well to arbitrary camera locations. Instead, it is more suitable to apply an aggregation strategy that either uses all per-detection scores of a trajectory or aggregates over a proportional fraction of the trajectory.

Percentile-based Aggregation

In percentile-based aggregation, instead of taking a fixed number of top per-detection scores in a trajectory, we aggregate all per-detection scores above a fixed percentile threshold p , such as the 90th percentile. Let

$$k_p(j) = \max\left\{i \in \{0, \dots, N_j\} : s_{(i),j} \geq \text{percentile}_p\left(s_{(1),j}, \dots, s_{(N_j),j}\right)\right\}, \quad (4.5)$$

be the index of the smallest score s that is at least as large as the p -th percentile of that trajectory's per-detection scores.

The percentile-based aggregation functions are defined as follows:

$$\textit{Percentile average: } \text{score}_{\text{avg}}^{(p)}(j) = \frac{1}{k_p(j)} \sum_{i=1}^{k_p(j)} s_{(i),j}, \quad (4.6)$$

$$\textit{Percentile median: } \text{score}_{\text{med}}^{(p)}(j) = \text{median}\left(s_{(1),j}, \dots, s_{(k_p(j)),j}\right), \quad (4.7)$$

$$\textit{Percentile lin. weighted average: } \text{score}_{\text{wavg}}^{(p)}(j) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{k_p(j)} (k_p(j) - i + 1) s_{(i),j}}{\sum_{i=1}^{k_p(j)} (k_p(j) - i + 1)}. \quad (4.8)$$

Figure 4.9 presents the NDCG results for the percentile-based aggregation functions for each camera location. The x-axis is shown on a logarithmic scale to highlight the high-percentile regions, where the 99th percentile corresponds to aggregating only the top 1% of per-detection anomaly scores within each trajectory, and the 0th percentile corresponds to aggregating over the entire trajectory.

Overall, the results are consistently worse than those obtained with the top- k aggregation. A possible explanation is that most anomaly categories are not dependent on the trajectory length. For example, failing to yield typically occurs within just a few seconds, both for vehicles that appear only briefly in the scene and for those that remain longer in the camera scene. This characteristic is better captured by the top- k aggregation, which focuses on the most informative anomaly scores rather than depending on the overall trajectory length. Moreover, the percentile plots confirm that on Monon Elm Street the most effective strategy is to aggregate only a small fraction of the highest per-detection scores within each trajectory, whereas on the Rangeline cameras aggregation over longer portions of the trajectories proves more beneficial.

Figure 4.9: NDCG results for percentile-based aggregation functions across the three cameras. The x-axis is on a logarithmic scale to emphasize high percentiles.

Weighted average on full trajectory

To define a single well-performing aggregation function that generalizes to arbitrary camera scenes, we propose a compromise aggregation function that integrates the insights from the previous experiments. Specifically, we include the entire trajectory in the aggregation, which is beneficial for Rangeline 116th Street, while still assigning more weight to the highest per-detection scores, which is crucial for Monon Elm Street.

To achieve this, we introduce an exponentially weighted average aggregation, which generalizes the linearly weighted average used earlier by introducing a tunable parameter a . The trajectory score is defined as

$$\text{Exponentially weighted average: } \text{score}_{\text{exp}}^{(a)}(j) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_j} a^{i-1} s_{(i),j}}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_j} a^{i-1}} \quad (4.9)$$

(a) Rangeline Medical Drive (b) Rangeline 116th Street (c) Monon Elm Street

Figure 4.10: NDCG results for exponentially weighted average aggregation functions across decay parameters a . The NDCG achieved by ASYM1 with $a = 0.98$ is highlighted.

where N_j is the length of trajectory j , and $a \in (0, 1)$ is a parameter that controls the weighting decay. Smaller values of a put stronger emphasis on the top-ranked scores, while values closer to 1 approximate the unweighted average over the full trajectory.

Figure 4.10 shows the NDCG results for the exponentially weighted average aggregation across different decay parameters a . The peaks on each camera achieve NDCG values comparable to those of the top- k aggregation, which so far provided the best results. Importantly, the optimal values for a are similar across the three camera scenes, with peaks consistently observed in the range $a \in [0.9, 1]$. On Monon Elm Street, strong performance is also achieved for smaller values such as $a = 0.7$ or $a = 0.8$, since smaller a emphasizes the highest per-detection scores. Still, performance remains high around $a = 0.9$ and $a = 0.95$ on Monon Elm Street, reaching NDCG values between 0.75 and 0.8, close to the overall optimum of 0.82 achieved with ASYM2.

Choosing a General Model Configuration and Trajectory Ranking Function

Table 4.6 summarizes the best NDCGs across all model configurations and trajectory scoring functions. The strongest results are obtained with $\text{score}_{med}^{(k)}$, $\text{score}_{avg}^{(k)}$, $\text{score}_{wavg}^{(k)}$, and $\text{score}_{exp}^{(a)}$. Given the high performance of the PMF models with exponentially weighted average aggregation and the fact that the peaks occur at similar a values across cameras, $\text{score}_{exp}^{(a)}$ is selected as the trajectory aggregation function for future use in our anomaly detection system.

Selecting a single PMF model configuration remains more difficult. No single model achieves the best results across all three cameras. ASYM2, for example, performs best on Monon Elm Street and Rangeline Medical Drive but is among the weakest on Rangeline

Camera	Best NDCG	ASYM1 & $\text{score}_{exp}^{(0.98)}$
Rangeline Medical Drive	0.81	0.75
Rangeline 116th Street	0.60	0.54
Monon Elm Street	0.82	0.75

Table 4.5: Comparison of best overall NDCG results with the chosen compromise configuration ASYM1 and $\text{score}_{exp}^{(0.98)}$.

Method	$\text{score}^{(k)}$	$\text{score}_{med}^{(k)}$	$\text{score}_{avg}^{(k)}$	$\text{score}_{wavg}^{(k)}$	$\text{score}_{med}^{(p)}$	$\text{score}_{avg}^{(p)}$	$\text{score}_{wavg}^{(p)}$	$\text{score}_{exp}^{(a)}$
Rangeline Medical Drive								
SYM0.5	0.60	0.64	0.68	0.65	0.62	0.64	0.62	0.64
ASYM0.5	0.61	0.65	0.67	0.65	0.63	0.65	0.63	0.65
SYM1	0.65	0.73	0.74	0.71	0.67	0.66	0.63	0.71
ASYM1	0.66	0.73	0.75	0.76	0.68	0.68	0.67	0.76
SYM2	0.64	0.74	0.73	0.70	0.67	0.65	0.63	0.71
ASYM2	0.75	0.80	0.81	0.79	0.69	0.68	0.68	0.79
Rangeline 116th Street								
SYM0.5	0.55	0.57	0.60	0.59	0.58	0.60	0.59	0.59
ASYM0.5	0.54	0.56	0.59	0.58	0.57	0.58	0.57	0.58
SYM1	0.48	0.56	0.54	0.52	0.55	0.53	0.51	0.54
ASYM1	0.50	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.56	0.57	0.56	0.55
SYM2	0.53	0.56	0.55	0.51	0.54	0.50	0.49	0.52
ASYM2	0.53	0.55	0.52	0.48	0.54	0.50	0.45	0.50
Monon Elm Street								
SYM0.5	0.76	0.76	0.77	0.76	0.72	0.72	0.72	0.77
ASYM0.5	0.80	0.80	0.79	0.79	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.80
SYM1	0.78	0.78	0.79	0.78	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.78
ASYM1	0.79	0.79	0.78	0.79	0.73	0.72	0.72	0.78
SYM2	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.70	0.70	0.70	0.76
ASYM2	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.82

Table 4.6: Best NDCG values across all model configurations and aggregation functions for the three camera scenes. Bold values indicate the maximum for each camera.

116th Street. Conversely, ASYM0.5 and SYM0.5 yield the best results for Rangeline 116th Street but perform poorly on Rangeline Medical Drive. As a compromise, we choose ASYM1, which achieves consistently good performance across all cameras for $a > 0.9$, as illustrated by the green dotted curve in Figure 4.10.

Finally, we fix the parameter a for the exponentially weighted average. We select $a = 0.98$ as a balanced compromise: it is optimal for ASYM1 on Rangeline Medical Drive, slightly below the argmax for Rangeline 116th Street, and slightly above the argmax for Monon Elm Street. The resulting NDCGs are shown in Table 4.5 and marked with a black cross in Figure 4.10.

Figure 4.11 illustrates the distribution of anomaly categories for the three camera scenes when using ASYM1 with $\text{score}_{exp}^{(0.98)}$. The histograms show the top 10, top 20, and top 50 anomaly candidates by trajectory score. Including the best 10 and best 20 highlights the anomaly types that are ranked especially highly. Despite the relatively small number of dangerous anomaly categories (red), the final configuration consistently ranks these categories at the top, so that many appear already within the top 10 and top 20. Particularly at Rangeline Medical Drive and Monon Elm Street, the majority of detected anomalies are of relevance degree 2 or higher, indicating high precision. The

(a) Rangeline Medical Drive

(b) Rangeline 116th Street

(c) Monon Elm Street

Figure 4.11: Distribution of anomaly categories among the top 10, top 20, and top 50 ranked trajectories for ASYM1 with score_{exp}^(0.98). Higher proportions of dangerous categories (red) among the top candidates indicate higher ranking precision.

higher amount of less relevant anomalies at Rangeline 116th Street aligns with the lower NDCG scores consistently observed for this camera across all models and aggregation functions.

It is important to note that the mapping of anomaly categories to relevance degrees can influence the evaluation outcomes. For example, if fast driving is considered only “relevant” rather than “highly relevant”, the resulting NDCG values change slightly. Moreover, since NDCG inherently accounts for all relevance degrees, the metric reflects overall ranking quality without focusing on specific categories or exclusively on the most dangerous anomalies.

4.4.2 AU-PR - Performance per Relevance Degree

To complement the NDCG analysis, we consider classical threshold-based metrics. Metrics such as Precision, Recall, and the area under the Precision–Recall curve (AU-PR) are

based on binary decisions of true or false positives and negatives. Standard multi-class adaptations assume mutually exclusive classes, which does not align with our relevance degree-setup. For example is every highly relevant anomaly (degree 3) also relevant (degree 2). Therefore, we retain the binary setup and define the positive class by thresholding the relevance degrees from Table 4.2. We evaluate the following four settings:

- relevance degree ≥ 1 : all anomalies are positives, regardless of severity
- relevance degree ≥ 2 : only relevant or more severe anomalies are positives
- relevance degree ≥ 3 : only highly relevant anomalies are positives
- relevance degree ≥ 4 : only the most dangerous anomalies are positives

Given a trajectory ranking function and the per-detection scores of a model, we rank all trajectories in the labeled data pool that are not labeled as mistakes (category -1). From this ranking, we compute Precision–Recall curves and the area under the curve (AU-PR). AU-PR thus serves as the metric for comparing models in this section. We focus on the four positive-class settings above and compare PMF models with NNC. For consistency, we use the initial ranking function score^(k), since it applies to both PMF and NNC. Figure 4.12 shows AU-PR as a function of $k \in [1, 50]$.

The AU-PR results per relevance degree reveal several noteworthy patterns. However, for anomalies of relevance degree 4, the number of available samples is too small to draw reliable conclusions, resulting in unstable PR curves in the right graphics.

When considering all anomalies (relevance degree ≥ 1), the NNC model performs weakest, showing the lowest AU-PR values. The performance gap to the PMF models narrows with increasing relevance thresholds, and for anomalies of relevance degree ≥ 3 , NNC performs at a comparable level. This, however, requires careful interpretation. In this setting, detections with relevance degrees < 3 are treated as false positives. While penalized in the metric, these anomalies are still more informative than genuine false positives, which are the detections of label 0, the "normal" trajectories. As a consequence, since PMF models detect more anomalies of relevance degrees 1 and 2 than NNC, the usefulness of these PMF detections is underestimated, and the performance of NNC might appear stronger than it actually is.

Compared to the NDCG curves in Figure 4.7, the AU-PR curves most closely resemble those of the setting “relevance ≥ 3 ,” particularly for Monon Elm Street. This indicates that anomaly candidates of at least “high relevance” have a particularly strong influence on the NDCG. Such anomalies typically appear at the top of an ideal ranking and therefore contribute disproportionately to the NDCG score. In our anomaly detection scenario, a large share of anomalies in the labeled data pool belong to relevance degree 3, which explains why this category effectively dominates the overall NDCG performance.

Moreover, the model configuration ASYM2, which achieves the best NDCG on Monon Elm Street and Rangeline Medical Drive, does not consistently perform best in AU-PR. For example, when maximizing detection performance across all anomalies (“relevance ≥ 1 ”), ASYM2 may not be the optimal choice. Overall, AU-PR results vary little across PMF configurations, except for “relevance ≥ 2 ” and “relevance ≥ 3 ” on Rangeline Medical Drive, where ASYM2 noticeably outperforms other settings.

Figure 4.12: AU-PR results for ranking function score^(k) across the three camera scenes and four relevance degree settings. Each curve shows the mean AU-PR over five PMF models per configuration, with shaded areas indicating ± 0.5 standard deviations. Results for NNC are shown as black dotted curves.

4.4.3 Robustness to Mistakes in Agent Detections and Tracks

To assess the robustness of our anomaly detection models against errors in the input data, we investigate the effect of including erroneous detections and tracking mistakes (category -1) in the evaluation. For this analysis, trajectories labeled as -1 are assigned to relevance degree 0 and considered in the top 50 candidates when present. Table 4.7 reports NDCG values using the initial and best-performing ranking functions score^(k), score^(k)_{avg}, and score^(a)_{exp}. The table presents the best results of the previous sections where we excluded label -1 for direct comparison next to the results of this section including category -1 trajectories. All performance decreases of at least 0.05 are highlighted in red.

The results show that Monon Elm Street is unaffected by including category -1 trajectories. This is consistent with Figure 4.3, which indicates almost no erroneous detections

Method	score ^(k)		score ^(k) _{avg}		score ^(a) _{exp}	
	excl. -1	incl. -1	excl. -1	incl. -1	excl. -1	incl. -1
Rangeline Medical Drive						
SYM0.5	0.60	<i>0.59</i>	0.68	<i>0.59</i>	0.64	<i>0.57</i>
ASYM0.5	0.61	<i>0.61</i>	0.67	<i>0.58</i>	0.65	<i>0.57</i>
SYM1	0.65	<i>0.65</i>	0.74	<i>0.67</i>	0.71	<i>0.65</i>
ASYM1	0.66	<i>0.66</i>	0.75	<i>0.71</i>	0.76	<i>0.72</i>
SYM2	0.64	<i>0.64</i>	0.73	<i>0.72</i>	0.71	<i>0.70</i>
ASYM2	0.75	<i>0.75</i>	0.81	0.81	0.79	0.79
Rangeline 116th Street						
SYM0.5	0.55	0.53	0.60	<i>0.51</i>	0.59	<i>0.51</i>
ASYM0.5	0.54	0.52	0.59	<i>0.50</i>	0.58	<i>0.49</i>
SYM1	0.48	<i>0.48</i>	0.54	<i>0.50</i>	0.54	<i>0.49</i>
ASYM1	0.50	<i>0.49</i>	0.57	0.53	0.55	<i>0.51</i>
SYM2	0.53	0.53	0.55	0.52	0.52	<i>0.49</i>
ASYM2	0.53	0.52	0.52	<i>0.50</i>	0.50	<i>0.47</i>
Monon Elm Street						
SYM0.5	0.76	<i>0.76</i>	0.77	<i>0.77</i>	0.77	<i>0.77</i>
ASYM0.5	0.80	<i>0.80</i>	0.79	<i>0.79</i>	0.80	<i>0.80</i>
SYM1	0.78	<i>0.78</i>	0.79	<i>0.79</i>	0.78	<i>0.78</i>
ASYM1	0.79	<i>0.79</i>	0.78	<i>0.78</i>	0.78	<i>0.78</i>
SYM2	0.76	<i>0.76</i>	0.76	<i>0.76</i>	0.76	<i>0.76</i>
ASYM2	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82

Table 4.7: Robustness analysis of anomaly detection models under input errors. NDCG results are shown for different ranking functions, comparing evaluations that exclude versus include category -1 trajectories. Values in red highlight performance decrease of at least 0.05 due to input mistakes. Best results for both exclusion and inclusion of category -1 are shown in bold.

or tracks in this scene. The camera perspective provides close, clear views of vehicles, leading to higher input data quality.

For the Rangeline cameras, models with a longer prediction horizon of $\delta = 2$, SYM2 and ASYM2, remain robust. They show negligible or no performance decrease. In contrast, models with shorter horizons SYM0.5, ASYM0.5 and SYM1 experience the largest decrease, with NDCG differences of up to 0.1. On Rangeline Medical Drive, this widens the performance gap between PMF configurations. For instance, with score^(k)_{avg}, SYM0.5 performs nearly 0.2 worse than ASYM2, underlining the importance of careful model selection when input data is prone to errors. On Rangeline 116th Street, SYM0.5 and ASYM0.5 are no longer the only best-performing models once category -1 trajectories are included. Instead, ASYM1 with score^(k)_{avg} and SYM2 with score^(k) also reach the top performance, each achieving an NDCG of 0.53.

Among the three ranking functions, score^(k) proves the most robust across all cameras. Its stability likely stems from relying only on the k -th highest per-detection score. During

labeling, we observed that bounding-box jumps and ID switches often create isolated high anomaly scores. For large k , $\text{score}^{(k)}$ is unaffected by such outliers, while ranking functions like $\text{score}_{avg}^{(k)}$ and $\text{score}_{exp}^{(a)}$ that include all top per-detection scores inevitably include scores from input mistakes in their calculation.

In summary, for applications with low-quality detections and tracking, we recommend using $\text{score}^{(k)}$ together with a longer prediction horizon in the PMF anomaly detector, for example, the ASYM2 configuration.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

This thesis addressed trajectory-level anomaly detection in static, overhead traffic scenes by proposing and evaluating probabilistic movement forecasting (PMF) models. This chapter summarizes the key contributions in Section 5.1, discusses its limitations in Section 5.2, outlines directions for future work in Section 5.3, and concludes with final reflections in Section 5.4.

5.1 Summary of Contributions

Modeling approach. We proposed a probabilistic movement forecaster (PMF) for anomaly detection that deliberately departs from the video-based prediction and reconstruction paradigms common in traffic anomaly detection. Rather than relying on full trajectory histories or time-windowed input, the PMF conditions on the current vehicle detection and its surrounding agents to estimate motion plausibility. This design directly addresses the challenges of static overhead scenes, where anomalies are often subtle, collective, and context-sensitive, and cannot be reliably inferred from an individual trajectory history. Prior state-of-the-art methods such as future-frame prediction [LLLG18] or reconstruction autoencoders [GLL⁺19] often fail in this setting, as they can easily reconstruct or predict apparently simple but anomalous events, such as a straight wrong-way trajectory or excessive speeding.

In contrast, the PMF outputs a probabilistic prediction of a traffic agent’s near-future positions, parameterized as a Gaussian distribution, and evaluates anomaly likelihoods through the Mahalanobis distance between predicted and observed outcomes. Its novelty lies in three contributions:

1. **Context integration:** Surrounding traffic agents are explicitly modeled as additional input channels, enabling detection of interaction-based anomalies.
2. **Distance-aware regularization:** A new training objective adjusts covariance magnitudes according to vehicle distance in the scene, enforcing tighter bounds for small, distant objects and greater flexibility for nearby ones.
3. **Asymmetric scoring:** An extension of the Mahalanobis distance adds direction-specific skew, improving sensitivity to perspective and motion uncertainties.

Together, these elements yield per-detection anomaly scores that are interpretable, probabilistically grounded, and robust to perspective variation. Aggregating these scores into trajectory-level rankings with advanced functions further ensures consistent evaluation and practical deployment across diverse scenes and anomaly types.

Evaluation framework. We curated a labeled data pool from three camera locations and evaluated rankings with NDCG@50 (NDCG), complemented by AU-PR analyses to

probe performance at different anomaly severity levels. Importantly, our dataset goes beyond typical anomaly benchmarks by providing 32 fine-grained anomaly categories and explicit degrees of relevance, rather than a single generic anomaly label. The inclusion of detection and tracking mistakes (label -1) ensures that evaluations remain robust against input noise, a common challenge in real-world deployments. Each of our three urban scenes contributes 24 hours of recorded detection and tracking data for training plus 48 hours with 1027 anomaly annotations for evaluation. Importantly, we include the full 48 hours of test footage, not just the annotated segments, so the evaluation reflects the real-world class imbalance: normal traffic highly dominates, and methods that excel at detecting the anomalies are also assessed for false positives on normal data. Our dataset establishes a unique and comprehensive foundation for benchmarking future traffic anomaly detection models and can easily be extended to further camera scenes. The dataset will soon be expanded with more highly relevant anomalies by adding short video clips of anomalous behavior observed during deployment at Starwit. We are convinced that ranking-based evaluation is the most appropriate framework for traffic anomaly detection because some anomalies are inherently more severe than others. Hence graded metrics such as NDCG capture practical priorities more faithfully, and are often underutilized compared to AU-PR or AU-ROC.

Aggregation functions. Since the models output anomaly scores per detection, we require aggregation functions to combine these into a single trajectory-level score. We formalized and tested various scoring functions, including the k -th best per-detection score, mean and linear-weighted averages of the top- k scores, percentile-based variants, and an exponentially weighted average over the entire trajectory. Across scenes, the exponentially weighted average score $_{\text{exp}}^{(a)}$ achieved consistently high NDCG across the three cameras with peaks for similar weight decay a values, $a \in [0.9, 1.0]$, which simplifies deployment. The final PMF model and aggregation function deployed at Starwit is ASYM1 with score $_{\text{exp}}^{(0.98)}$, which proved a strong compromise across all cameras.

Robustness to input noise. We further examined robustness against detection and tracking mistakes (label -1). Longer-forecasting horizon models (ASYM1/SYM2/ASYM2) showed the highest resilience, with NDCG scores differing by at most 0.04 between clean input data and noisy input. Among aggregation strategies, the k -th best score proved most robust overall, likely because it discards isolated spurious spikes that averaging-based approaches must absorb.

5.2 Limitations and Discussion

Label scarcity and scene coverage. Fewer than 2,000 labeled trajectories across three cameras limit the statistical confidence of fine-grained model comparisons. Moreover, anomaly types are not evenly distributed across locations: for example, Monon Elm Street, a pedestrian-oriented intersection, contains many driving-beside-the-road anomalies, whereas the two high-traffic roundabout scenes are dominated by cutoffs, near collisions, and illegal turns. Expanding both the number of labeled samples and the diversity of camera scenes is therefore crucial to ensure reliable evaluation and to capture the full spectrum of real-world traffic anomalies. Beyond scarcity, anomaly candidate labeling is often subjective, as some cases may plausibly fit multiple categories, while others differ subtly from existing examples of the same type.

Metric sensitivity to relevance mapping. Since NDCG explicitly weights anomalies by graded relevance, any change in the category-to-degree mapping can shift results. For example, if “fast driving” were assigned degree 2 instead of degree 3, the relative ranking performance would change accordingly. This means that for applications where the notion of “most relevant” differs from our definition, NDCG scores should be recalculated, and a different PMF configuration or aggregation function might be more suitable than our final choice, ASYM1 with score_{exp}^(0.98).

Unknown-pose generalization. For vehicle positions and orientations far outside the training support, such as off-road or unusual headings, PMF behavior becomes unreliable. Although the model could in principle assign a high Mahalanobis distance by hallucinating implausible predictions, in practice it often inflates its variance estimate, reflecting uncertainty. This large variance reduces the Mahalanobis distance, and thus downgrades some cases that should be flagged as highly anomalous. This effect is visible in Figure 4.5a (images 2 and 3) in Chapter 4, where the model encounters an unfamiliar heading and predicts a broad covariance. Addressing this will require incorporating the predicted variance directly into the anomaly score to prevent safety-critical anomalies from being down-weighted or overlooked.

Scene heterogeneity. We observed that the “best” aggregation window depends on scene dynamics: small k for top- k aggregations excel where a few frames carry decisive evidence, for instance wrong-way turns, while larger windows help where anomalies unfold over longer spans, such as slow, hesitant driving. This motivates adaptive aggregation, such as a data-driven span selection or scene-adaptive scoring, rather than a single universal aggregation with fixed hyperparameters.

5.3 Future Work

Whole-image context. Our pipeline operates on tracked agents and their local context. Extending to full-frame image modeling would incorporate road layout, signage, temporary obstacles, and rare participants such as animals or debris that fall outside current “vehicle/pedestrian/bike” abstractions. This could improve the detection of subtle anomalies that are only interpretable with global context. However, we would need to make sure the pipeline remains robust to lighting, weather, and background variation. Additionally, we could combine a scene encoder with the PMF outputs to extract the semantic map or occupancy of the streets, similar to the semantic scene understanding from the Cityscapes dataset [COR⁺16]. Hence, trajectory plausibility is judged against both learned motion priors and global scene constraints.

From anomalies to anomaly types. The current system ranks anomalies without distinguishing their type, meaning we know that the model predicts the current situation as unusual but not whether it corresponds to, for example, wrong-way driving, speeding, or a cut-off. Future work should aim to enrich detection with anomaly categorization. A simple direction would be geometric rule induction, for instance comparing the current position with predicted and actual observed future motion to detect reversed, fast, or off-course driving. For example, if predicted and actual future position lie on opposite sides relative to the current heading, indicate wrong-way or reverse driving. A more advanced approach would be to add a follow-up unsupervised clustering to our anomaly

detection pipeline. The idea is to learn low-dimensional representations for anomalous snippets and find clusters in the representations that align with types. Deep clustering methods such as DEC [XGF15], VaDE [JZT⁺16], DeepCluster [CBJD19], or SCAN [GVG⁺20] could be used to group anomalies into semantically meaningful categories without manual supervision. Vector Quantized Variational Autoencoders (VQ-VAE) could learn to reconstruct typical anomalous situations or simplified scenes. Their discrete latent space tends to form natural clusters of different behavioral patterns, providing a foundation for automatically categorizing anomalies.

Out-of-distribution handling. As already mentioned in the discussion part, highly unusual events, such as vehicles far off-road or in unseen poses, require more robust recognition. A hybrid approach combining out-of-distribution detection with our PMF Mahalanobis distance anomaly scores and calibrated uncertainty could ensure that such anomalies are flagged reliably rather than down-weighted.

Adaptive aggregation. Our results showed that the optimal aggregation window is scene-dependent. Short spans are well-suited for sharp anomalies such as wrong-way driving, while longer spans better capture slow-developing behaviors like hesitant driving. A promising direction is to replace fixed parameters with data-driven approaches, for instance, learning-to-rank or reinforcement-learning strategies that adapt aggregation spans dynamically to scene properties such as traffic density or interaction complexity. Moreover, incorporating human feedback during runtime could enable adaptive refinement of aggregation, allowing the system to align more closely with user priorities and improve continuously in deployment.

Scaling datasets and benchmarks. Finally, progress requires broader evaluation. Expanding the number of labeled samples will improve statistical confidence and capture the full spectrum of real-world traffic anomalies. Larger-scale, shared benchmarks will also enable fairer comparisons and lead to further advances in anomaly detection for static overhead traffic scenes.

5.4 Conclusion

This thesis demonstrated that anomaly detection in static, overhead traffic scenes benefits most from conditioning probabilistic predictions on surrounding agents and from carefully designed trajectory-level aggregation. By decoupling motion plausibility from temporal video histories, the proposed Probabilistic Movement Forecaster (PMF) directly addresses the unique challenges of high-distance overhead views, where anomalies are often subtle, context-dependent, and interaction-based.

Our findings show that severity-aware evaluation with ranking-based metrics such as NDCG is central to assessing anomaly detection in traffic scenes. With further advances in uncertainty calibration, adaptive aggregation, anomaly-type clustering, and broader benchmarks, the field can move beyond “detecting what looks odd” toward early, precise, and actionable anomaly detection in complex traffic environments.

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